

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools

PROJECT

Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools

AGREEMENT NUMBER

LC-01624438/101018048

D.1.1 – State of the Art and Audit

SUBMISSION DUE DATE

Month 2

DELIVERABLE VERSION

V2.0

Co-funded by
the European Union

DELIVERABLE TITLE	State of the Art and Audit
DELIVERABLE No.	D.1.1.
Deliverable Version	V2.0
Deliverable Filename	D1.1 – State of the Art and Audit
Nature Of Deliverable	R
Number Of Pages	45
Work Package	WP1. Baseline Mapping
Partner Responsible	NUIG
Author(s)	Sara Gartland & Paul Flynn
Contributor(s)	Maria Ana Carneiro, Jose de Sousa Fialho, Greg Holloway, Clare Cullen, Emma Hamilton, Amy Harris, Ioannis Poulourtzidis
Reviewed by	Joe Cullen
Approved by	Panos Bamidis, Project Coordinator

PROJECT FULL TITLE	Living Labs and Open Toolkit for the co-design of accessible IT systems and tools
Start Of Project	1 April 2021
Duration	12 months
Project URL	https://liveit-project.eu/
Disclaimer	The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Contents

LIST OF ACRONYMS	4
LIST OF FIGURES.....	5
LIST OF TABLES.....	5
1. INTRODUCTION	7
1.1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE	8
1.2. INTENDED AUDIENCE	8
1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE.....	9
1.4. RELATION TO OTHER WPS & TASKS.....	9
2. METHODS.....	9
2.1. SEARCH PROCEDURES	9
2.2. INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA	14
2.3. SEARCH RETURNS AND SCREENING PROCESS.....	16
3. RESULTS.....	18
3.1. POLICY AND GUIDELINES	18
3.1.1. Guidelines.....	20
3.1.2. Policies	23
3.2. STUDIES.....	25
3.2.1. Methods	27
3.2.2. Tools and Platforms	28
3.2.3. Policy and Guidelines	29
3.2.4. Experiences of People with Cognitive Disabilities	29
3.2.5. Studies Involving People with Cognitive Disabilities Broadly Defined.....	30
3.2.6. Studies Involving People with Specific Cognitive Disabilities.....	30
4. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER DISCUSSION	31
5. D.1.1 REVISION – GREY LITERATURE ADDENDUM	33
5.1. METHODS.....	33
5.2. FINDINGS	35
5.2.1. Related H2020 Projects.....	35
5.2.2. Policies and Guidelines.....	36
5.2.3. Research Methods.....	40
5.2.4. Designing for People with Cognitive Disabilities	41
5.2.5. Community Resources.....	42
5.2.6. Centre People with Cognitive Disabilities.....	44
6. REFERENCES	45
6.1. POLICY	45
6.2. STUDIES.....	50
6.3. TOOLS	62

LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
ATAG	Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines
UAAG	User Agent Accessibility Guidelines
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
UNCRPD	United Nations Convention on Rights of Persons with Disabilities
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WAI	Web Accessibility Initiative
WAI-ARIA	Web Accessibility Initiative – Accessible Rich Internet Applications

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 – Initial Search Return Screening..... 17
Figure 2 – Further Search Return Reduction and Categories..... 18
Figure 3 – Major Policies and Guidelines 19
Figure 4 – WCAG 2.0..... 22
Figure 5 – Best Practice Lab Methods 27

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 – Search Strings..... 10
Table 2 – Search Term Possibilities for Google Searches 14
Table 3 – Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria..... 15
Table 4 – Guidelines PDFs Reviewed in Detail..... 20
Table 5 – Policy PDFs Reviewed in Detail 24
Table 6 – Study PDFs Reviewed in Detail 26
Table 7 – Initial Search Terms..... 34
Table 8 – Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Grey Literature Search 34
Table 9 – Related H2020 Projects..... 36
Table 10 –Policy Items 37
Table 11 – W3C Guidelines and Related Documentation 39
Table 12 – Research Methods 41
Table 13 - Designing for People with Cognitive Disabilities 41
Table 14 - Community Resources 43
Table 15 - Resources that Centre People with Cognitive Disability 44

Disclaimer Statement

The content of the publication herein is the sole responsibility of the publishers and does not necessarily represent the views expressed by the European Commission or its services. While the information contained in the document is believed to be accurate, the authors(s) or any other participant in the LIVE-IT consortium make no warranty of any kind with regard to this material including, but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose. Neither the LIVE-IT Consortium nor any of its members, their officers, employees or agents shall be responsible or liable in negligence or otherwise howsoever in respect of any inaccuracy or omission herein, or direct, indirect, special, incidental or consequential damages in connection with the furnishing, performance, or use of this material.

Statement of Originality

This Deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

Copyright

© The LIVE-IT Consortium, consisting of:

- Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis (AUTH), Greece
- Arcola Research LLP (ARC), United Kingdom
- National University Of Ireland Galway (NUIG)
- Universidade Catolica Portuguesa (UCP), Portugal

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License, 2017. For details, see <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>. The text, figures and tables in this report can be reused under the provisions of this License. Logos and other trademarks are not covered by this license. The content of the documents marked as restricted or confidential are not to be disclosed externally without prior written consent from the LIVE-IT Consortium.

Acknowledgements

The LIVE-IT team would like to thank all of our collaborating partners, especially those organisations working with us on the ground in developing the Co-Labs, and all of the LIVE-IT ‘users’ – people with cognitive disabilities – for giving their time and insights to contribute to this research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Against the background of the increased digitisation of almost all aspects of life and accelerated digitisation due to COVID-19, the LIVE-IT project aims to address the urgent needs associated with web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. The overarching goal for the LIVE-IT project is to aggregate and valorise the insights and findings of different ‘research lenses’ on the relationship between cognitive disabilities and digital inclusion into actionable experimentation spaces, in order to support inclusive accessibility by tailoring design to the settings in which people with cognitive disabilities engage with digital technologies in their everyday ‘lifeworld’. To accomplish this goal, the LIVE-IT project is broken up into several work packages, the first of which addresses the state-of-the art with respect to web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities.

Work Package 1 establishes the initial knowledge base and sets up activities to be carried out in the co-labs developed within the project. There are four co-labs, one co-lab per each of the LIVE-IT research partners. The co-labs are constructed as follows:

- *Life Skills Lab* (Coimbra): Focuses on navigating and managing interactions with ‘the system’, including consumer transactions and related issues such as understanding contracts and small print; filling in forms; consumer rights; online security and protection; managing dates and appointments
- *Emergencies Lab* (London): Focuses on reducing risk and increasing preparedness and resilience in emergency situations – both at the everyday level, for example health e-consulting, and at the large scale, such as the COVID pandemic – covering finding information, looking for help and support, understanding emergency procedures and instructions
- *Self-Development Lab* (Galway): Focuses on supporting people to take advantage of the opportunities provided by digital technologies for learning, employment, personal development, involving navigation, information searching, information processing, understanding text and graphics and using animations, working with authoring systems
- *Help & Support Lab* (Thessaloniki): Focuses on using online information and guidance systems, for example searching for and using public information tools, using complex interfaces and gateways, identifying key points from dense and ‘official’ documentation, navigating through guidelines

The following report details the purpose, methods, and findings from the state-of-the-art baseline review conducted within Task 1.1 of Work Package 1. Generally speaking, the objective of Task 1.1 was to develop a rapid yet comprehensive picture of the state-of-the-art of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities through academic and grey literature searches. In the next section, more detail is provided about the purpose of Task 1.1 and this review.

1.1. PURPOSE AND SCOPE

This task uses a ‘scientific realist review’ method (Pawson et al, 2005) to map the landscape of inclusive web accessibility, focusing on the perspective of people with cognitive disabilities. The review entails an iterative process of: searching the field for successful theory, policies and practices to support inclusive web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities; applying quality criteria to the material identified, based on relevance and rigour to produce a short list of examples; producing a final shortlist of examples; analysing the material collected to produce a comprehensive review of state of the art; integrating the results to re-assess the original ‘map’ of the field, and to add new examples.

To focus this review, one overarching research question and several sub-questions were developed. The review question guiding this work is:

- What is the state-of-the-art of interventions that support web accessibility for citizens, ages 9 and up, living with cognitive impairment?

The sub-questions that add focus to this overarching question are:

- What are examples of good practices – ‘interventions’- including examples of platforms and tools - that have the potential to support inclusive web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities?
- What is the impact of successful initiatives, interventions or programmes on supporting inclusive web accessibility for people with cognitive impairment?
- What are the similarities and differences between successful initiatives, interventions or programmes supporting web accessibility for people with cognitive impairment in the different sectors (i.e. education, health, commerce, employment, etc...)?
- What are the drivers and barriers, or supports and constraints, for web accessibility for people with cognitive impairment?
- What are the key characteristics of successful initiatives, interventions or programmes on supporting inclusive web accessibility for the population under this study?
- What recommendations can be made for the future initiatives that wish to support web accessibility for citizens living with cognitive impairment?

1.2. INTENDED AUDIENCE

This document should be used as a reference by:

- European Commission
- Policy Makers

- Stakeholders
- LIVE-IT Project Team

1.3. STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE

The following report begins with the methods for the academic and grey literature searches carried out in Task 1.1. Then, screening procedures are provided so that the search conducted for this task can be replicated as the field advances. Next, the results of the search are reported. Finally, the report concludes with a discussion of implications for subsequent work within the LIVE-IT project.

1.4. RELATION TO OTHER WPS & TASKS

The state-of-the-art and audit conducted during Task 1.1 feeds directly into all other Work Packages in the LIVE-IT project. In Work Package 1, Task 1.1 added to the Task 1.2 tools and platforms audit. In Work Package 2, Task 1.1 informed best practices for co-lab methods and the development of scenarios. In Work Package 3, Task 1.1 will have contributed to features of the Open Toolkit via the identification of tools, platforms, and scenarios for the co-design labs. In Work Package 4, Task 1.1 will have contributed to the development of the makerspaces within the co-design labs, again, via the identification of tools, platforms, and scenarios for the co-design labs. Finally, Task 1.1 is contributing to Work Package 5 by generating manuscripts for publication; as of the project review in October, two manuscripts related to the Task 1.1 search methods and search results will have been submitted for review.

2. METHODS

The web accessibility baseline described in this report was developed through a realist review (Pawson et al, 2005), which involves a review of state of the art in the field as a ‘halfway house’ between a ‘systematic review’ and a ‘narrative review’. The specific sources for the review include both official literature –existing research reviews and reports, bibliographic databases and academic research – and ‘grey’ literature: unpublished material like blogs and dissertations.

2.1. SEARCH PROCEDURES

The following databases were systematically searched using fifteen-year time limited search strings: Web of Science, SCOPUS, EBSCOhost, ERIC and ProQuest. A total of 50 search strings were developed and entered into the databases. Table 1, below, shows the set of search strings used. Internet searching through Google Scholar was carried out as well as forward and backward

tracking of citations from studies that are included in the review. Given the multi-jurisdictional aspect of the study, local searches of the grey literature were included in this review to capture information relevant to each co-lab location. Table 2, below, shows possible combinations of search terms that were used in the local grey literature and Google searches to capture additional results relevant to the unique locations for the co-labs.

The result of the search has been downloaded and saved to a standard database accessible to all project team members. Duplicate results were removed. The titles and abstracts of all remaining studies were screened by a process informed by the study inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are provided in detail in the next section. All stages of the screening process are illustrated in Figure 1, below.

Table 1 – Search Strings

Search Number	Search String
S1	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "web accessibility"
S2	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "web accessibility"
S3	"complex need*" AND "web accessibility"
S4	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "e-services"
S5	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "e-services"
S6	"complex need*" AND "e-services"
S7	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "e-commerce"
S8	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "e-commerce"
S9	"complex need*" AND "e-commerce"
S10	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "e-health"
S11	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "e-health"
S12	"complex need*" AND "e-health"

S13	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "e-learning"
S14	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "e-learning"
S15	"complex need*" AND "e-learning"
S16	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "online learning"
S17	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "online learning"
S18	"complex need*" AND "online learning"
S19	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "e-banking"
S20	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "e-banking"
S21	"complex need*" AND "e-banking"
S22	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "online banking"
S23	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "online banking"
S24	"complex need*" AND "online banking"
S25	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "web accessibility tool*"
S26	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "web accessibility tool*"
S27	"complex need*" AND "web accessibility tool*"
S28	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "user-centered design"
S29	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "user-centered design"
S30	"complex need*" AND "user-centered design"
S31	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "accessibility widgets"
S32	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "accessibility widgets"
S33	"complex need*" AND "accessibility widgets"

S34	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*") AND "assistive technology"
S35	(neurodiverse OR neurodivergent) AND "assistive technology"
S36	"complex need*" AND "assistive technology"
S37	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "web accessibility"
S38	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "e-services"
S39	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "e-commerce"
S40	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "e-health"
S41	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "e-learning"
S42	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "e-banking"

S43	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "online learning"
S44	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "online banking"
S45	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "web accessibility tool*"
S46	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "user-centered design"
S47	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "accessibility widgets"
S48	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder") AND "assistive technology"
S49	(dyslexia OR aphasia OR "non-verbal" OR "down syndrome" OR "autism" OR "dyscalculia" OR "cognitive decline" OR "attention deficit disorder" OR "learning disabilit*" OR "intellectual disabilit*" OR dysgraphia OR dementia OR "cerebral palsy" OR "brain injury" OR "motor neurone disease" OR "irlen syndrome" OR "pervasive developmental disorder")AND ("web authoring tool*" OR "web evaluation tool*")

S50	("cognitive impairment*" OR "cognitive deficit*" OR "cognitive disabilit*" OR neurodiverse OR neurodivergent OR "complex need*") AND ("web authoring tool*" OR "web evaluation tool*")
-----	--

Table 2 – Search Term Possibilities for Google Searches

General keyword group	Specific keywords
Web accessibility	Accessibility, Digital, ICT, Internet, Digital Inclusion
Cognitive disability	Dyslexia, Aphasia, Non-verbal, Dysarthria; Dyspraxia; Dementia; Alzheimer's disease; Intellectual Disability; Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD); Autism; Asperger syndrome; Dyscalculia; Downs syndrome; Motor Neurone Disease; Brain injury; Stroke; Cerebral palsy
Type item and/or issue	Policy, Guidelines, E-Health, E-Commerce; E-Service; E-Banking; Social Media, Distance Learning; Online Safety

2.2. INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Table 3, below, provides an overview of the inclusion/exclusion criteria for the review. As noted in the previous section, searches were limited to a 15-year window: 2006-2021. We decided on the 15-year window as opposed to a more standard 10-year window, because the first iPhone was released in 2007. We expected that a sharp increase in accessibility related literature might have occurred around 2007. Due to the fact that we could not identify any literature reviews specifically addressing web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities, we felt it important to capture any related literature from at least 2007. Expanding the window to 15 years allowed us to capture the time leading up to and immediately following this watershed date.

The database search included peer reviewed studies published in English. However, if a study published in an alternate language is deemed relevant it was included. In addition, works that are returned through the grey literature search will be considered for inclusion if they are returned in EU members state languages other than English and deemed relevant by the project team.

The review focused on citizens ages 9 and up who live with cognitive impairment. The lower age limit of 9 years was set to capture the year prior to the transition from primary school to

secondary school across the multiple jurisdictions represented in this research partnership. No upper age limit was set, because the need for web accessibility when living with cognitive impairment does not diminish or stop at any particular age. In the instance where studies included participants determined to be outside of the study age range, if the mean age range of the study is 9 years of age or greater, the study was included subject to agreement by the project team members. Studies that did not focus exclusively on citizens with cognitive impairments and where the datasets presented by the study are not presented separately will be excluded from this review.

Table 3 – Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

Component	Inclusion	Exclusion
Publication	2006-2021 Published in English in peer reviewed journals and/or full conference proceedings Grey literature search returns that present comprehensive reports on relevant programmes and adhere to the criteria below	Any publication prior to 2006 Not in English, abstracts only, editorials, letters. Duplicate publications Conference proceedings not presenting full papers
Geographic Location	Any geographic location	No geographic location excluded
Study Design	All study designs	No study design excluded
Population	Any age 9 years and older Experiencing Cognitive impairment	Ages younger than 9 years Not experiencing cognitive impairment
Intervention	All intervention types focused on the target population	Any intervention not focused on the target population

Comparison	All studies to be included irrespective of the presence of comparator or control group	No exclusions based on comparison group(s)
Outcome	Data and results reported	Studies not reporting any data or results

2.3. SEARCH RETURNS AND SCREENING PROCESS

A comprehensive search was conducted to determine the state of the art of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. Figure 1 and Figure 2 below summarise the search process. To begin, all 50 search strings (see Table 1) were entered into the Scopus, ProQuest, Web of Science, and ERIC databases. This returned a total of 263,410 results. The results were imported to Mendeley and duplicates were removed. Removal of duplicates brought the total number of search returns to 214,719. Then, the remaining search returns were limited to peer-reviewed documents, which further reduced the number of returns to 112,521.

At this point, the title and abstract of every remaining item was screened to determine inclusion and exclusion (see Table 3). In the case that inclusion or exclusion could not be determined by reading the title and abstract, the full PDF was accessed to make the decision. After this round of screening, only 140 items remained.

Figure 1 – Initial Search Return Screening

The PDFs were accessed for all 140 items, which were then categorised prior to reviewing the papers. Three categories were created based on the goals of the review and the needs of the co-design labs: Policy/Guidelines, Studies, and Tools. The Policy/Guidelines category included all papers related to state and/or institutional policy and guidelines for web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities, and 44 papers were placed into this category. The Studies category included all papers reporting on web accessibility studies involving people with cognitive disabilities, and 55 documents were placed into this category. The Tools category included all papers reporting on specific tools and/or platforms related to web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities, and 41 documents were placed in this category.

As can be seen in Figure 2, only two of the three categories are included in this report: Policy/Guidelines, and Studies. The documents from the Tools category were used to populate a Baseline Catalogue that feeds into Tasks 1.2, 1.3, and 1.4 of Work Package 1 (reported in a separate deliverable). Additionally, the papers in the Tools category did not meet the inclusion criteria for the review. Using the structure of the search as a framework, this report is organised into three sections: Policy and Guidelines, Studies, and Tools.

Figure 2 – Further Search Return Reduction and Categories

3. RESULTS

The results of the Task 1.1 search are reported in this section in two main categories, as depicted in Figure 2, above. The categories structuring the reporting of results are policy/guidelines and studies. Following the results, the report will conclude with a discussion of how the results inform Task 1.2 and other elements of the LIVE-IT project.

3.1. POLICY AND GUIDELINES

Initial screening in this category produced a long list of 44 articles focused on policies and/or guidelines across multiple countries. At this stage, PDF versions of the 44 articles were retrieved and read to make final decisions about inclusion in the review. This stage of screening further reduced the reviewable results to 17 articles. Articles were excluded if they focused exclusively on the United States context and/or failed to specify cognitive disability. Of the 17 articles reviewed in detail, 9 focused primarily on existing or developing guidelines and 8 focused on policies.

The geographic distribution of the policies and/or guidelines in the 17 articles reviewed are as follows: 4 from the UK (1 policy, 3 guideline articles), 2 from Italy (1 policy, 1 guideline article), 1

from the USA (0 policy, 1 guideline article), 2 from Portugal (1 policy, 1 guideline article), 1 from Slovenia (1 policy, 0 guideline articles), and 5 from the EU in general (4 policy, 1 guideline article). Tables 4 and 5, below summarize the paper type, publication date, and geographic distribution information for the articles reviewed. Additionally, Figure 3 provides an illustration of how the major policies and guidelines are related. Of the countries where labs will be hosted, two were not represented in the search returns: Ireland and Greece. Thus, a Google search was conducted to ensure that relevant policies and guidelines from Ireland and Greece were included in this review. Such Google searches did not return additional articles. Rather, the supplemental searches led us directly to government websites stating the relevant local policy for Ireland and Greece.

One policy and one set of guidelines appear to serve as the framework for the state policies reviewed. The United Nations (UN) Convention on Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) is the overarching policy that both informs and drives the EU and individual state policies. Additionally, the World Wide Web Consortium’s (W3C’s) Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) serve as a foundation for EU and individual state policies. The review of the policy and guideline articles revealed that only parts of the CRPD and the WCAG are specifically included in the EU and individual state policies. Namely, the CRPD and the WCAG are more comprehensive and rigorous in their targets for accessibility than the EU and individual state policies. Figure 1, below, displays how the policies and guidelines are related.

Figure 3 – Major Policies and Guidelines

3.1.1. Guidelines

This section provides a more detailed description of the relevant findings from reviewing the 9 articles focused on existing or developing guidelines. Some articles were empirical, meaning that they involved an empirical test of web accessibility using a particular set of existing guidelines as a framework for testing, a review of existing guidelines for web accessibility, or used an empirical approach to develop new and/or more focused sets of guidelines for web accessibility. Table 4, below, provides an overview of the article types, publication date, and geographic location of these 9 articles.

The dominant set of guidelines for web accessibility, broadly speaking, are the W3C's WCAG. These guidelines have been revised since their introduction. The WCAG 1.0 were released in 1999 and subsequently incorporated into policy recommendations around the world. A decade later, the WCAG 2.0, which included additions and revisions to the WCAG 1.9, were released. The WCAG 2.0 are what appear in most policies, and are organized around the acronym POUR, as illustrated in Figure 4, below. POUR stands for Perceivable-Operable-Understandable-Robust, and these descriptors link to specifications for web pages and web apps that support accessibility at three different levels. The WCAG levels are labelled as A, AA, and AAA. Most policies require WCAG compliance at the AA level, which means that most policies do not require the highest level of accessibility. Figure 4 also captures the additions to the WCAG in versions 2.1 and 2.2. It is important to note that the WCAG is an open-source-like set of guidelines, meaning that all discussion around changes to the guidelines are public.

One major critique of the WCAG has been the lack of accessibility specifications to support people with cognitive disabilities. W3C as an organisation have recognised this problem and developed the COGA Task Force, whose mission is to improve current accessibility standards and recommend new accessibility standards focused on people with cognitive disabilities. Figure 4 also highlights the specifications in the WCAG 2.0 that support accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. Minimal research exists on how effective the existing standards are for people with cognitive disabilities, however.

Table 4 – Guidelines PDFs Reviewed in Detail

Citation	Year	Paper Type	Country/Region
(Al-Mauwil et al, 2019)	2019	Empirical	UK
(Chadwick et al, 2013)	2013	Review	UK

(Dattolo et al, 2017)	2017	Empirical	Italy
(Goncalves et al, 2013)	2013	Empirical	Portugal
(James et al, 2014)	2014	Empirical	n/a
(Lewthwaite, 2014)	2014	Commentary	UK
(Moulin, 2010)	2010	Empirical	EU
(Raymaker et al, 2019)	2019	Empirical	USA
(Zhang et al, 2020)	2020	Empirical	n/a

Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2

Identified by WC3 COGA Task Force as supporting accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities

Blue = Conformance Level A
 Green = Conformance Level AA
 Red = Conformance Level AAA

* = Added in Version 2.1
 ** = Added in Draft Version 2.2

Figure 4 – WCAG 2.0

Articles focused on guidelines also provided useful definitions and frameworks that may be relevant to the lab development, lab implementation, and data analysis stages of the LIVE-IT project. Al-Mawil, et.al. (2019) provided a clear distinction between e-inclusion and e-adoption. E-inclusion “is mostly concerned with the social impact of relative differences in ICT use between different socioeconomic groups and individuals” where e-adoption “focuses instead on absolute and average figures of ICT uptake and their economic impact.” Additionally, Raymaker, et.al. (2019) present a method for building and testing websites and online platforms with people with cognitive disabilities alongside a framework for considering information accessibility that has three dimensions: physical, intellectual, and social. The methodology employed by Raymaker, et.al. (2019) began with qualitative interviews to develop an understanding of participants’ (people with cognitive disabilities) experiences with healthcare websites. Then, design cycles were initiated around the content, the user interface, and the interactive survey tool to be used in the actual study. These design cycles involved researchers and people with cognitive disabilities. Following this step, the healthcare website to be tested in the actual research study was tested with participants (people with cognitive disabilities) in an alpha and a beta stage. Revisions to the website were made based on feedback from the alpha stage, which was then tested again in the beta stage. LIVE-IT will take the process described in Raymaker, et.al. (2019) and apply it to multiple scenarios in multiple co-design labs.

Although informative, there are issues with the articles focused on guidelines that were reviewed for this project. First, if empirical, the studies are often framed via a deficit mindset. In other words, the frameworks, research questions, and findings tend to focus on what is wrong with the people under investigation rather than what can be improved about the websites. When there is a focus on improving the websites, the focus is primarily on text readability. Second, if theoretical, the papers or reviews tend to speak about disability more generally. Thus, there is a distinct lack of empirical and theoretical exploration into web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities.

3.1.2. Policies

This section provides a more detailed description of what was learned from reviewing the 8 articles focused on policies. Articles involving policy for web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities were either empirical in nature, literature reviews, or law reviews. If empirical, the paper typically reported on automated testing of specific pages of specific websites against a policy in a specific region. Reviews provided more wholistic views of how policies and guidelines worked together to produce the current state of policy regarding web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities.

Both EU and individual state policies have taken steps to essentially codify the WCAG. Three EU-level policies drive this effort in the four countries in which LIVE-IT labs will be located: The European Standard for Accessibility Design (EN 301 549), the European Disability Strategy, and the European Web and Mobile Accessibility Directive. Within Ireland, Portugal, the UK, and Greece,

policies have been enacted that either directly adopt the EU policies listed above or adopt add to the EU policies. Additions are usually in the form of requiring higher levels of WCAG conformance.

Articles focused on policies also present gaps in the literature worth filling. First, if empirical, the studies reviewed tended to rely on automated accessibility testing with limited human-computer interaction of any sort. While this is useful information that can reduce the number of research hours that need to be spent on basic accessibility issues, this method excludes the experiences, perceptions, desires, and needs of people who are actually using the website, app, or device. It is worth noting that the automatic checking of website accessibility typically reveals dismal levels of accessibility from only checking a single page. Second, if theoretical, the paper or review tends to focus on the historical backgrounds of the policies without providing clear pathways for future research with people with cognitive disabilities. Third, the policy articles reviewed tended to frame disability very broadly or focus on physical disabilities such as vision impairments. Finally, this review did not return any articles providing insight into how the policies have influenced the real-world usability and accessibility of websites and web applications for people with cognitive disabilities.

Table 5 – Policy PDFs Reviewed in Detail

File Name	Year	Paper Type	Country/Region
(Barricelli et al, 2021)	2021	Empirical	Italy
(Delarney et al, 2010)	2010	Review	UK
(Ferri, 2018)	2018	Review	EU
(Giannoumis, 2014)	2014	Empirical	UK and Norway
(Kim, 2020)	2020	Empirical	USA & Europe
(Kous et al, 2021)	2021	Empirical	Slovenia
(Muchagata, 2019)	2019	Empirical	Portugal
(Timmers, 2008)	2008	Review	EU

3.2. STUDIES

The search results included 55 articles reporting on studies involving people with cognitive disabilities, which means that at least one well-defined group of participants within the study were people with cognitive disabilities *and* at least one goal of the study was to investigate some element of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. Unfortunately, 9 PDFs were not able to be accessed. Thus, a total of 43 articles were reviewed in detail. Table 6, below, shows the full list of studies reviewed (by citation) organized by search-term related subtopics: web accessibility, user-centered design, assistive technology, e-health, e-learning, and e-banking. Articles written in English, Spanish, Portuguese, and Italian were located. No articles in Greek were returned in the searches.

Table 6 – Study PDFs Reviewed in Detail

Web Accessibility	User Centered Design	Assistive Technology	E-Health	E-Learning	E-Banking
(Holz, 2021) (Karreman et al, 2007) (Krivec et al, 2020) (Kvikne, 2021) (Moreno et al, 2012) (Morris et al, 2018) (Ophoff et al, 2021) (Passerino, 2007) (Rocha et al, 2012) (Rocha et al, 2016) (Santham, 2012) (Williams, 2013) (Williams, 2015) (Wu et al, 2019) (Yaneva et al, 2019)	(Lazar et al, 2018)	(Beentjes et al, 2020) (Benda, 2015) (Brunskill, 2020) (Fickas et al, 2008) (Gillespie-Lynch et al, 2014) (Gomez et al, 2017) (Hedman et al, 2016) (Heyn et al, 2021) (Kwan et al, 2020) (Lancioni et al, 2014) (Malinowsky et al, 2010) (McCarron et al, 2019) (Moisey et al, 2007) (Oksnebjerg et al, 2020) (Scott et al, 2013) (Wallcook et al, 2019) (Zhu et al, 2019)	(Malinowsky et al, 2014) (Zaagsma et al, 2020)	(Andreasen, 2019) (Arbelaitz et al, 2016) (Igo et al, 2006) (MacFarlane et al, 2009) (Ngubane-Mokiwa, 2021) (Williams, 2017) (Williams, 2020)	(Hahn et al, 2018)

A review of these studies painted a picture of the state of the art for web accessibility in six main areas: Methods, Tool/Platforms, Policy/Guidelines, Experiences of People with Cognitive Disabilities, Studies Involving People with Cognitive Disabilities Broadly Defined, and Studies Involving People with Specific Cognitive Disabilities. These six main areas structure the remainder of this section.

3.2.1. Methods

The studies reviewed revealed two themes with respect to research methods. First, they provide examples of the methods used to date and the types of findings they can produce. Second, they provide a glimpse of more innovative methods such as the co-design approach the LIVE-IT labs will adopt. Figure 4, below, shows how more popular methods used to date and more innovative methods combine to create some best practice recommendations for the LIVE-IT labs.

Figure 5 – Best Practice Lab Methods

Accessibility testing and usability testing that involves people with cognitive disabilities tends to involve researcher-developed websites or web applications. This happens for multiple reasons. Often the rationale is to control particular variables, to limit the number of pages, or to allow for specific modifications. There are two notable downfalls of this approach. First, this prevents the observation of challenges associated with navigating through multiple pages and/or navigating

from one site to another. Second, this prevents the exploration of real-world challenges and barriers.

The majority of the studies reviewed involved text-based websites or web applications. For example, when studying information seeking, researcher-developed websites containing various levels of text-based information (simple through complex) might be used. Unfortunately, this limits the production of knowledge around how to adequately provide non-text-based methods for sharing information on the internet. Additionally, the solutions often involved presenting less material, which robs people with cognitive disabilities of developing the same sorts of understandings people who can read the complex text might develop about a particular topic.

To build websites and/or web applications, researchers often take a phased approach that involves people with cognitive disabilities at multiple stages. Initial phases often include a pilot with feedback from participants representative of the target user group. Then, revisions take place based on the pilot data. After revisions are made, the formal study takes place, which involves user testing and/or evaluations of the website or web application. In some instances, multiple design cycles take place. This mirrors the type of approach proposed for the LIVE-IT labs.

Finally, co-design and participatory design research methods tended to yield the most relevant results. What we mean by this is that the findings from studies using these methods tended to produce tools and findings that were relevant to the lives of people with cognitive disabilities. The results also tended to be anchored in real-world scenarios rather than highly controlled experimental scenarios. Such studies often involved about 10 participants who engaged in design cycles that progressed from problematizing to designing to experimenting.

3.2.2. Tools and Platforms

As noted in the section above, many researchers opted to develop their own websites or web applications for their studies. However, some researchers used existing apps, including:

- Google apps
- FindMyApps (very poorly rated by users in study)
- iOS Maps
- Mobile Coach Technology (preferred when used with human assistance also)
- Social Support Aid (very poorly rated by users in study)
- Read & Write
- ICanEmail
- ReACT (very poorly rated by users in study)
- DigiContact
- Existing Social Media Apps (iOS and Android)
- Existing Messenger Apps (iOS and Android)

- Newham Easy Read
- WebHelpDyslexia

Regardless of the type of website or app (built by the researcher or already existing), a few common challenges arose. First, there is often too much text on the websites or web apps. Participant feedback across multiple studies highlighted the need for more non-text options, more real photo (as opposed to animated) options, and more audio options. Also, participants warned that when non-text options drastically increased the amount of scrolling required, the solution was no better than the initial problem of too much text. Second, the cognitive load associated with searching for and selecting information from the web was frequently highlighted as problematic. Participants often had to pre-search terms or phrases for use in databases to ensure correct spelling, for example. Additionally, participants reported having to toggle between multiple sites/tools/platforms to accomplish tasks without errors, relying on image searches to avoid frustration due to spelling errors, and experiencing difficulty with filtering and verifying the accuracy of search results. Third, when the steps to open or navigate the website or web app were too complex, participants tended to abandon the website or the application during the study.

3.2.3. Policy and Guidelines

This section is included to prove a point mentioned earlier in the report. Very few studies explicitly link their findings to existing web accessibility policies or guidelines. The studies reviewed here are no exception. In the instances that guidelines were referenced, authors cited (but did not go into detail about) the WCAG. In the instances that policy was referenced, it was typically in the American context. Thus, very little is known about the real impacts that policies and guidelines for web accessibility in the European context are influencing the lives of people with cognitive disabilities.

3.2.4. Experiences of People with Cognitive Disabilities

The majority of the studies reviewed included data from either interviews, surveys, focus groups, or some combination of the three aimed at gathering participant perceptions of and experiences with web accessibility. Several interesting themes arose from this type of data. Even if the website or web app met the highest WCAG standards, if it was not relevant to or immediately useful for the participants, then participants tended to dislike the website/web app or rate it poorly (Arbelaitz, et.al., 2016; Benda, 2015; Beentjes, et.al., 2020; Oksnebjerg, et.al., 2020). Then, beyond pure accessibility or usability, other things that are important to people with cognitive disabilities, such as opportunities to build community, share their true identities, and share expertise (Andresean, 2019; Moisey, et.al., 2007). Finally, tools and platforms that serve to replicate existing social hierarchies or systems of exclusion need to be improved. Participants often cited social media sites in comments related to this theme (Gillespie-Lynch, et.al., 2014; Ngubane-Mokiwa, 2021; Zhu, et.al., 2021).

Additional details categorised by disability type are provided below. Please note, while the overarching goal of the LIVE-IT project is to improve web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities rather than cater to specific sub-groups of that target population, most of the studies reviewed were developed for specific target populations. Thus, accurately interpreting their results involves contextualising the studies through consideration of the characteristics of the study samples.

3.2.5. Studies Involving People with Cognitive Disabilities Broadly Defined

One subset of studies involved participants described as having “intellectual disabilities,” “learning disabilities,” “cognitive disabilities,” “cognitive impairment,” and “mild cognitive impairment.” These studies tended to involve information seeking and information gathering through text-based websites. Balasuriya, et. al. (2021) presented people with cognitive disabilities with web articles in “simplified” and “summarised” form and found that the use of images, familiar words, and larger font sizes influenced participants’ understanding of the information presented. Although most participants found the information easier to read, some participants noted that the experience did not satisfy their desire for knowledge because less information was provided. Karreman, et.al. (2007) also provided participants with two versions of a website (home page only) to pilot an easy-to-read website design, and results showed that the easy-to-read website being piloted seemed to improve participants’ efficiency in seeking and reading information. However, only a single webpage was used, which is typical of the studies reviewed and highlights the need to explore more complex situated in real-world contexts. Rocha, et. al. (2012) also compared multiple types of webpage navigation – text-based and image-based navigation – and results indicated that image navigation increased the speed of task-completion.

Some studies provided more in-depth views of participants’ experiences and delved further into user experience than efficiency and task completion. Moreno, et.al. (2012) highlighted the fact that people with cognitive disabilities often experience frustration associated with errors due to repeatedly clicking on items and perceiving delays in webpage loading as personal errors. Brunskill (2020) spoke with students with learning disabilities and learned that students often relied on Google to proofread search terms, which adds nuance to the understandings of efficiency in information seeking developed in studies presented above. Namely, the interaction with the link that takes an individual to the information needed is far from the only element in the web accessibility puzzle in online information seeking.

3.2.6. Studies Involving People with Specific Cognitive Disabilities

Within the set of papers reviewed three more specific groups of participants with cognitive disabilities appeared frequently: people with memory issues (i.e. dementia, aging, or concussion), people with autism, and people with dyslexia. Interestingly, studies involving each of these different groups tended to focus on issues of web accessibility related to text. People with

concussions (Beaton, et.al., 2021) and people with memory loss related to dementia and/or old age (McCarron, et.al., 2019; Wallcook, et.al., 2019) benefit from the inclusion of audio, video, and picture modes of sharing information. Similarly, people with autism benefit from webpages with limited scrolling and direct navigation pathways (Eraslan, et.al., 2019; Yaneva, et.al., 2019).

The majority of the studies that included a specific group of people with cognitive disabilities explored web accessibility issues for people with dyslexia (de Avelar, et.al., 2015; Gupta, et.al., 2019; Holz, 2021; Krivec, et.al., 2020; Kvikne, 2021; MacFarlane, et.al., 2009; Morris, et.al., 2018; Ophoff, et.al., 2021; Wu, et.al., 2019). These studies all explored elements of text-based webpages or web applications, and highlighted a need for more graphical and/or visual presentation of online information. Overwhelmingly, the studies focused on specific elements of text, such as font size, amount of text, and text color with an emphasis on participant accuracy and comprehension. While these are important areas of study, the focus on such areas leaves gaps in knowledge. Some studies reviewed highlight specific gaps. Morris, et.al. (2018) show that query formulation and refining results in academic searches are barriers for students with dyslexia. Ophoff, et.al. (2021) noted that problems associated with the creation and management of passwords, distorted fonts on CAPTCHA's, and other login-related challenges also created persistent barriers for people with dyslexia.

Additionally, the search returned a few studies involving people with Down Syndrome, people with cerebral palsy, and people with Huntington Disease (Gomez, et.al., 2017; Hahn, et.al., 2018; Lazar, et.al., 2018; Santham, 2012). Generally speaking, these studies focused on the usability of particular tools and/or platforms, which is related to accessibility. Santham (2012) showed that using a Wii remote allowed people with cerebral palsy to more comfortably navigate webpages. Lazar, et.al. (2018) provided an in-depth look at conducting design research with people with Down Syndrome, which contributed to the methodological recommendations in the previous section. Gomez, et. al. (2017) investigated the ways in which an Android app developed to support people with Down Syndrome as they navigated workplace tasks and found that the combination of audio, visual, and haptic information supported participants in task completion.

4. CONCLUSION AND FURTHER DISCUSSION

The Task 1.1 state-of-the-art search developed a baseline for the existing policies and guidelines, empirical investigations, and tools and platforms for web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities within the academic and grey literature. As noted in the introduction, Task 1.1 supports all other tasks and work packages in the LIVE-IT project in some way. Thus, the results reported above have significant implications for the project as well as the public.

First, in the remainder of Work Package 1, a tools and platforms audit – Task 1.2 – will also feed into the co-design lab development and Open Toolkit. Task 1.1 supported Task 1.2 by producing a

list of 41 PDFs that included tools and/or platforms that could potentially be included in the developing tools and platforms catalogue. As noted in the body of this report, the 41 PDFs specifically related to tools and platforms were not included in the results of the literature review, because the articles did not fit the inclusion criteria. However, the tools and/or platforms included in these PDFs were likely to be of interest in the Task 1.2 catalogue development. Thus, the 41 PDFs were split among partners for entry into a preliminary catalogue for use in Task 1.2. Additionally, all tools and platforms identified in the articles reviewed (i.e. those listed in the results section) were also entered into the preliminary catalogue for Task 1.2. Finally, the fact that many of the tools and platforms located during the Task 1.1 searches were not co-designed with nor have yet to be tested by people with cognitive disabilities highlights the importance of the LIVE-IT co-design goals.

Second, in Work Package 2, the LIVE-IT research consortium is undertaking lifeworld analysis to explore the everyday digital experiences of people with cognitive disabilities and developing scenarios for the four co-design labs. The results of this review frame and provide theoretical backing for the experiences of people with cognitive disabilities collected and analysed during the lifeworld analyses. For example, lifeworld interviews in the UK and Ireland are suggesting that people with cognitive disabilities rely on toggling between Google and other sites or apps as a self-developed work-around to cope with non-accessible web environments, and the academic literature shows that this is an empirically documented barrier for people with cognitive disabilities. The combination of published empirical data and recently collected lifeworld data highlighting a specific challenge is supporting the development of scenarios related to this challenge to be tested in the co-design labs. Additionally, gaps in the literature, namely a lack of co-design and co-evaluation with people with cognitive disabilities, supports the claim that the work to be done in the tasks for Work Package 2 (and beyond) is urgent and necessary. Finally, best practices and methods gleaned from the literature is supporting the practical planning and implementation of lab activities.

Third, in Work Package 3, an Open Toolkit consisting of the tools that allow the four consortium labs to become active co-design spaces will be generated. Because this report has fed directly into Task 1.2 and Work Package 2, it will necessarily influence the development of the Open Toolkit. However, due to the innovative nature of the co-design labs, the Open Toolkit will likely improve upon and alter the methods, tools, and platforms identified in the state-of-the-art baseline and audit.

Fourth, in Work Package 4, the Makerspaces and Hackathons, which build upon the work done in earlier work packages will also necessarily relate back to the academic and grey literature searches reported here. Finally, with respect to Work Package 5, Dissemination, this state-of-the-art search and audit have already produced two manuscripts for review. It is likely that the results reported here will also continue to frame additional manuscripts submitted for publication during the lifetime of the LIVE-IT project.

5. D.1.1 REVISION – GREY LITERATURE ADDENDUM

The pace of publishing peer-reviewed literature is much slower than the pace of developments in the area of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. Therefore, we conducted a parallel grey literature search to our academic literature search. We consider *grey literature* to be resources that contribute to our understanding of the state of the art of web accessibility that are not strictly limited to peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. Such resources can include, but are not limited to: blog posts by experts in the field, deliverables from related H2020 projects, articles posted by relevant and trustworthy organisations, and other webpages or documents related to the topic of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities.

Our grey literature search paralleled the academic literature search in that it explored similar keywords, or search terms, but it also adapted to the needs of the project. What we mean by this is, the grey literature search was responsive to the gaps in the academic literature search, the needs of the four co-design labs, and the emergent findings coming out of the lifeworld analyses being conducted by each member of the LIVE-IT consortium. Thus, we consider this grey literature search to be a living document. While the academic search returns will not likely change much over the course of this one-year pilot project, the grey literature returns are more likely to change for fixed search terms. Additionally, the needs of the project will evolve throughout its lifetime, which will create new search terms and produce new lists of useful and relevant grey literature.

The following sections provide details of the grey literature search as of November, 2021. In the remaining deliverables for the project, we will include additions to the grey literature search and how they inform our evolving understanding of the state of the art of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. We begin with a description of our methods. Then, we present the findings organised by theme.

5.1. METHODS

This section presents the search methods and the inclusion methods for the grey literature search. The search methods refer to the process by which we located grey literature items. The inclusion methods refer to the process by which we selected grey literature items for inclusion in the review.

Search methods for the grey literature search were funnel-like in nature. The search process began with each member of the consortium using a list of recommended keywords (see Table 7, below) to develop search strings to be used in Google searches. We referred to these searches as *local Google searches*, because these searches were to be conducted using the keywords with a focus on developing a list of locally relevant and useful search returns. From here, subsequent rounds of Google searches were conducted to supplement the initial returns, further probe questions that arose from the academic literature search, and explore concepts illuminated by the lifeworld analyses.

Table 7 – Initial Search Terms

General keyword group	Specific keywords
Web accessibility	Accessibility, Digital, ICT, Internet, Digital Inclusion
Cognitive disability	Dyslexia, Aphasia, Non-verbal, Dysarthria; Dyspraxia; Dementia; Alzheimer's disease; Intellectual Disability; Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD); Autism; Asperger syndrome; Dyscalculia; Downs syndrome; Motor Neurone Disease; Brain injury; Stroke; Cerebral palsy
Type item and/or issue	Policy, Guidelines, E-Health, E-Commerce; E-Service; E-Banking; Social Media, Distance Learning; Online Safety

Inclusion methods for the grey literature search were initially developed to parallel the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the academic literature search. Table 8 provides an overview of how the inclusion and exclusion criteria for search returns was modified for the grey literature search. A 10-year window was used for the grey literature search, as opposed to the 15-year window for the academic literature search. As with the academic literature search, we would include any study or any intervention involving people with cognitive disabilities ages 9 and up. The area of the inclusion and exclusion criteria that needed the most attention as we conducted the search was the *Outcome* category.

Due to the evolving nature of the field of web accessibility, especially for people with cognitive disabilities, the development of tools and resources is outpacing the ability of those doing the developing to share evidence of implementation. Initially, we hoped to be able to locate at least initial forms of data associated with early implementation for all of the grey literature items included in our review. However, that proved to be too restrictive and eliminated too many highly relevant and useful items from our review. Therefore, we decided to evaluate all grey literature search returns not clearly included on the *Outcome* dimension by asking each consortium member to review the search returns and make recommendations for inclusion based on the following criteria: local relevance, author/origin, promise, and usefulness.

Table 8 – Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Grey Literature Search

Component	Inclusion	Exclusion
Publication	2011-2021 Published in English and/or languages appropriate for each lab's local context Any geographic location, but priority given to publications	Published before 2011 Not published in English or a language appropriate for any of the labs' local contexts No geographic location excluded

	from or highly relevant to each lab's local context	
Study Design	Any design	No study design excluded
Population	Citizens living with cognitive impairments, ages 9 and up	Citizens not living with cognitive impairments Younger than 9 years of age
Intervention	Any intervention type	No intervention type excluded
Comparison	No comparison (control) group required for inclusion	Lack of comparison (control) group is not grounds for exclusion
Outcome	Documented implementation (can be a pilot)	No documented implementation

As noted above, the grey literature review will be viewed as a living document to be updated throughout the lifetime of the project. As of November, 2021, the consortium members agreed to include 40 grey literature items. Some of these items are different pages of a parent website, and they are counted separately due to a difference in intended audience and/or subject matter. In the next section, we present the findings from the present version of the grey literature search.

5.2. FINDINGS

The findings from this grey literature search inform our understanding of the state of the art of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. More specifically, our review of the grey literature enhanced our understanding of the state of the art in six areas: related H2020 projects, policies and guidelines, research methods, designing for people with cognitive disabilities, community resources, and centring people with cognitive disabilities. Across all six categories, the need to further involve people with cognitive disabilities at all steps of the research process and the need to expand beyond the current prevalence of text-oriented tools are apparent. However, the sections that follow provide additional detail on the findings within each category.

5.2.1. Related H2020 Projects

Two related H2020 projects have contributed significantly to the state of the art for web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities in recent years. They are the Easy Reading Project and the Insension Project. The Easy Reading project worked to “develop a software for users with cognitive disabilities that supports them to access any webpage” by allowing for instantaneous personalisation involving symbolic, pictorial, and video adjustments. The Insension Project worked to “design and develop an ICT platform that enables persons with profound and

multiple learning disabilities” by supporting them as they process information and communicate their needs via technology. If required to rank the two projects in terms of relevance to LIVE-IT’s goals, the Easy Reading Project is most closely related. However, the knowledge produced by the Insension Project still contributes to the state of the art of web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities.

As shown in Table 9 the websites for the Easy Reading and the Insension projects provide multiple sources of valuable information. The Easy Reading Project makes major contributions in the areas of research methodology, user testing, and software development for and with people with cognitive disabilities. On the *Downloads* page within the Easy Reading website, a full set of ethics documents, practical checklists, risk management documents, and other items related to the collection and use of data with and from a vulnerable population are publicly available. Such documentation informed LIVE-IT’s ethical framework and procedures for Lifeworld Analysis and Co-Design Labs. The Insension Project adds to the plentiful resources described above by providing links to Deliverables and publications that focus on gathering training data for machine learning algorithms to be used within a platform for people with cognitive disabilities and the development of scenarios for testing.

Table 9 – Related H2020 Projects

Author	Description	Links
Easy Reading Consortium (Athena, Dart, FunkaNu, JKU, KI-I, PIKSL, Texthelp, TUD, W3C)	Information about the development and testing of the EasyReading software	https://www.easyreading.eu/the-project/ https://www.easyreading.eu/downloads/ https://www.easyreading.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Easy-Reading-Handbook.pdf
Insension Consortium (PSNC, PHHD, JSI, CTIC, NaTak, Harpo)	Information about the development and testing of the Insension platform	https://www.insension.eu/word-packages/ https://www.insension.eu/publications/

5.2.2. Policies and Guidelines

Policies and guidelines drive research and private sector projects related to web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities. In this section, we present findings related to policy and findings related to guidelines separately. Policy refers to standards for web accessibility that have been codified by various governments. Guidelines refer to standards that are widely used within the field, but not necessarily codified by governments in their full form. Generally speaking, most

policy on web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities is focused on a particular set of guidelines: the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG).

Table 10 –Policy Items

Title	Author	Brief Description	Link
What is the observatory?	Portuguese Observatory of Web Accessibility	Description of the Portuguese Observatory of Web Accessibility	https://observatorio.acessibilidade.gov.pt/
Web and mobile app accessibility	National Disability Authority: Centre for Excellence in Universal Design	Description of Irish accessibility requirements	https://universaldesign.ie/technology-ict/web-and-mobile-app-accessibility/
Digital Accessibility	General Secretariat for Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures	Description of the Greek system for recording and monitoring the compliance with accessibility requirements	https://www.secdigital.gov.gr/projects/psifiaki-prosvasimotita/

The academic literature search already presents the policies addressing web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities in the European Union, England, Greece, Ireland, and Portugal. Ongoing *local Google Searches* conducted to support co-lab development for the LIVE-IT project produced two additional grey literature items that are included in this portion of the review. Table 10 provides an overview of these items. It is worth noting that both of these resources define web accessibility more broadly than LIVE-IT does. While this project is specifically focused on web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities, the two resources presented below are focused on web accessibility in general. However, we include them here due to their local relevance.

First, in Portugal, an agency called The Observatory functions as an accessibility checker and tests public-entity websites for compliance with accessibility as defined by Portuguese law. As is the case for most web accessibility policy, Portuguese policy does not require the highest levels of compliance with the WCAG. However, the knowledge that The Observatory exists, and that it provides resources for web developers is useful, especially within the local context.

Second, in Ireland, an agency called the National Disability Authority (NDA) supports the development of accessible websites within Ireland. Within the NDA, the Centre for Excellence in

Universal design provides links to publicly available courses on universal design for web developers. Additionally, links to country-specific resources for designing accessible websites.

Third, in Greece, the EU legislation on accessibility has been incorporated by Law 4591/2019 (Government Gazette 19 / A / 12.2.2019), which establishes a comprehensive system for recording and monitoring the compliance of websites and applications for mobile devices in the public sector with accessibility requirements and at the same time, provides the possibility of citizen feedback through the mechanism of submission of comments / reports. Regarding the accessibility of websites and applications for mobile devices of public sector organizations, all ICT actions and projects will be designed from the beginning in accordance with the principle of universal design, so that they can be used by all people, to the greatest extent possible, without the need for adaptation or specialized design, without excluding assistive devices for specific groups of people with disabilities, where required.

It is worth noting that this section lacks grey literature resources specifically targeting the UK. In the case of the UK, many of the resources already included in the academic literature search and the tools and platforms search in Task 1.2 already address the UK context. Thus, consortium members did not see a need for more UK-specific resources at this time. The grey literature list may be updated as the project continues if that changes. In the case of Greece, the various searches have yet to return local resources. This may be due to the way in which we are conducting our searches, and this will continue to be addressed throughout the project.

Table 11 – W3C Guidelines and Related Documentation

Author	Description	Links
W3C	Information about accessibility standards and guidelines	https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/ https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/atag/ https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/uaag/ https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/aria/
W3C	Information about cognitive accessibility	https://w3c.github.io/coga/gap-analysis https://w3c.github.io/coga/issue-papers https://w3c.github.io/coga/user-research https://w3c.github.io/coga/content-usable/ https://w3c.github.io/coga/persona/

The academic literature search provided details about the W3C’s WCAG, which is the set of standards for web accessibility currently driving both policy and research. In addition to the WCAG, the W3C also provides additional sets of guidelines to extend accessibility beyond just the web content. Table 5 provides an overview of these guidelines and related documentation that was heavily influential in the design and development of the LIVE-IT project.

W3C provides three additional sets of guidelines to serve alongside the WCAG as tools for designing accessible websites and web apps. The Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines (ATAG) provide a framework for making authoring tools accessible, “so that people with disabilities can create web content,” and support the goal of creating more accessible web content. The User Agent Accessibility Guidelines (UAAG) explain how to make browsers, browser extensions, media players, readers, and other applications that render web content accessible to people with disabilities. Both the ATAG and the UAAG target developers and designers, and provide a roadmap for involving people with cognitive disabilities as developers and designers. Finally, the Web Accessibility Initiative Accessible Rich Internet Applications (WAI-ARIA) standards further support the development of accessible web content and web applications with a special focus on dynamic content and advanced user controls.

The WCAG, ATAG, UAAG, and WAI-ARIA all deal with accessibility in general. Therefore, a taskforce has been developed to specifically focus on accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities within the W3C's efforts. This taskforce is called COGA, and Table 11 also includes links related to COGA-specific documentation that has formed the foundation of work within the LIVE-IT project. These documents will be revisited in later sections.

5.2.3. Research Methods

The grey literature search also supplemented LIVE-IT's development of research methods for the co-design labs. As noted in the section on related H2020 projects, the Easy Reading ethics documentation formed the foundation of the ethics framework, procedures, and documentation for the LIVE-IT co-design labs. Table 12, below, provides an overview of additional resources that contribute to our understanding of the state of the art of research methods involving people with cognitive disabilities. In addition to the Easy Reading documentation, a literature review, a UNESCO publication, and a set of principles for design justice.

Both the literature review (not included in the academic literature search because it was not a study) and the UNESCO publication echo findings from all searches conducted to date. Namely, they support the fact that for real, relevant, and meaningful change to be made in web accessibility, people with cognitive disabilities must be involved in all aspects and at all stages. The authors of the literature review present an interesting framework for digital inclusion comprised of 5 dimensions: access to internet, sensorimotor challenges, cognitive challenges, technical challenges, and social codes and conventions. Each of these dimensions is further broken down into environmental factors and personal factors. This signals the importance of considering factors inside and outside the person when investigating web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities – meaning that research cannot only problematise the person. The UNESCO publication provides interesting data related to web accessibility for people with disabilities, broadly defined. However, the call to involve people with disabilities in future work is one that must be heeded.

In order to protect a vulnerable population within our research, we conducted searches that would inform our co-design procedures. This led us to the Design Justice Network's Principles. They are a set of 10 principles for co-design with a focus on social justice and the protection of all contributors. The Design Justice Network Principles complement the W3C guidelines discussed above by adding a relational and interpersonal element to our framework for co-design.

Table 12 – Research Methods

Title	Author	Brief Description	Link
Bridging the digital divide for people with intellectual disability	Lussier-Desrochers, et.al.	2-phase literature review of the challenges people with cognitive disabilities face with respect to digital inclusion	https://cyberpsychology.eu/article/view/6738/6204
Delivering Together for Inclusive Development: Digital Access to Information and Knowledge for Persons with Disabilities	Alireza Darvishy, Deniz Ercal, Juliet Manning	Reports focused on sustainable development goals related to universal design and web accessibility for people with disabilities	https://www.ospi.es/export/sites/ospi/documents/documentos/servicios-publicos-digitales/Inclusive-Development-UNESCO.pdf
Design Justice Network Principles	Design Justice Network	10 principles developed through open peer review for inclusive desing practices	https://designjustice.org/read-the-principles

5.2.4. Designing for People with Cognitive Disabilities

The grey literature resources listed in Table 13 below are separated from the section on guidelines. We made this distinction for two reasons. First, the majority of these resources are extensions of the WCAG with a specific focus on people with cognitive disabilities. Second, if they are not an extension of the WCAG, they are too context-specific to be considered guidelines in a general sense. These resources are heavily focused on text accessibility features, which makes sense because much of the website and web application content is text-based. However, it is becoming apparent that there is a lack of resources extending beyond enhancing the current text-saturated reality to a new non-text dominated version of the web.

Table 13 - Designing for People with Cognitive Disabilities

Title	Author	Brief Description	Link
Web Design Considerations for Cognitive Disabilities	Deque University	Descriptions of accommodating cognitive disabilities in web design	https://dequeuniversity.com/tips/web-design-cognitive-disabilities

Designing Mobile Apps for Use by People with Cognitive Disabilities	Level Access	Descriptions of how to design mobile applications with accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities in mind	https://www.levelaccess.com/designing-mobile-apps-for-use-by-people-with-cognitive-disabilities/
Mobile Application Accessibility Handbook	Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region	Handbook for designing mobile apps with accessibility features for people with disabilities	https://www.ogcio.gov.hk/en/our_work/community/web_mobileapp_accessibility/promulgating_resources/mahandbook/doc/mobile_app_handbook.pdf
How to create an accessible app (and why you should)	Caspar Geerlings	A set of best practices for mobile application design	https://medium.com/obero-namsterdam/how-to-create-an-accessible-app-and-why-you-should-5493f41f8bdb
Social Media User's Guide: Ensuring accessibility	University of Rochester	A set of best practices for individuals posting on behalf of the university	https://www.rochester.edu/social/guide/accessibility.html

5.2.5. Community Resources

The second to last category of grey literature search returns included in the review is labelled *Community Resources*. This category includes blog posts, how-to guides, and descriptions of accessibility tools whose target audience is, or at least includes, the community of people with cognitive disabilities. One might wonder why the table for this section, Table 14, is not infinitely long, as the LIVE-IT Project aims to produce an Open Toolkit for the community. Table 14 only includes the six resources listed, because the remainder of the tools and platforms that can be considered community resources are included in the database for D.1.2.

Table 8 provides an overview of the grey literature search returns labelled as community resources. Action Blocks, as a tool, will be included in the D.1.2 database of tools and platforms, but a support document for Action Blocks as well as a practitioner review of Action Blocks is included in this review. Action Blocks are innovative because they allow users to streamline complex sequences needed to execute tasks on their mobile phones and tablets in a highly personalised manner. Additionally, Action Blocks are for Android phones and tablets, which the majority of the LIVE-IT participants are using. Intrigued by the augmentative and alternative

communication (AAC) features of Action Blocks, we pursued additional searches related to AAC tools, which yielded two resources related to AAC tools for iOS devices.

In addition to the Action Block and other AAC resources, two other websites stood out as community resources due to their database-like nature. First, the IncludEdu provides a framework for organising existing applications from Apple, Microsoft, and Google within four dimensions: Communication and Interaction, Social-Emotional Learning and Mental Health, Sensory and Physical, and Cognition and Learning. Not only is this an exceptional and comprehensive database of tools, it is also an exemplary framework for considering the needs and challenges of people with cognitive disabilities in ways that do not overly medicalise the challenges or focus too much on a specific diagnosis. Second, the AbilityNet “how-to guides” are simple and easy to follow for all users, and they explain how to access and use various accessibility features that exist within operating systems.

Table 14 - Community Resources

Title	Author	Brief Description	Link
Use Action Blocks	Google	Description of Action Blocks	https://support.google.com/accessibility/android/answer/9711267?hl=en
AAC Resources: A Look at Google Action Blocks	Carole Zangari	Review of Action Blocks	https://practicalaac.org/practical/aac-resources-a-look-at-google-action-blocks/
AAC Apps	PRC Saltillo	Description of AAC apps for iOS	https://aacapps.com/
AssistiveWare: Proloquo2Go	AssistiveWare	Description of AAC app for iOS	https://www.assistiveware.com/products/proloquo2go
IncludEdu: Get Started	IncludEdu	Resources for educators seeking accessibility options for students	https://includedu.online/getstarted/
Simple "How To" Guides	AbilityNet	A series of "how to guides" provided via link for using accessibility features of various operating systems, etc...	https://mcmw.abilitynet.org.uk/

5.2.6. Centre People with Cognitive Disabilities

A prominent theme within the academic literature review is that research on web accessibility for people with cognitive disabilities needs to actively centre and involve people with cognitive disabilities. This theme has already been noted within the grey literature themes, as well. Therefore, we conducted searches focused on resources that centred people with cognitive disabilities. Beyond the related H2020 projects described above, there are two categories of grey literature that centre people with cognitive disabilities.

First, return to the Table 5, which provides an overview of the W3C resources most relevant to this project. The W3C COGA Task Force documents all centre people with cognitive disabilities. These resources include issue papers on cognitive accessibility, frameworks and recommendations for cognitive accessibility research (especially, user research), and resources related to involving people with cognitive disabilities and learning disabilities in research. Appendix A in the article on Making Content Usable for People with Cognitive and Learning Disabilities, which focuses on mapping user needs, personas, and patterns, is providing a framework for how the LIVE-IT Project will organise and track the user needs identified during Lifeworld Analysis and the literature reviews through the remainder of the project.

Second, consider Table 15, which contains the accessibility information for several social media sites identified during the Lifeworld Analysis as being the primary authoring tools used by LIVE-IT participants. Due to the fact that most of our participants have reported using social media as the only means for authoring content on the internet, we also conducted a search of various social media platforms' accessibility features. Not surprisingly, most of the accessibility features are text-centric. The academic literature review identified at least one study of an attempt to produce alternative social media networks for people with cognitive disabilities due to the fact that many of the existing social media sites are hostile environments for such individuals. However, the further investigation of how social media can be more accessible for people with cognitive disabilities is needed.

Table 15 - Resources that Centre People with Cognitive Disability

Title	Author	Brief Description	Link
Accessibility	Facebook	Descriptions of the accessibility features available through Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/help/273947702950567/?helpref=hc_fnav
How to make images accessible for people	Twitter	Descriptions of the accessibility features available through Twitter	https://help.twitter.com/en/using-twitter/picture-descriptions

How do I edit the alternative text for a photo on Instagram?	Instagram	Descriptions of the accessibility features available through Instagram	https://help.instagram.com/503708446705527
Accessibility	LinkedIn	Descriptions of the accessibility features available through LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/accessibility
Accessibility	Slack	Descriptions of the accessibility features available through Slack	https://slack.com/intl/en-ie/accessibility
Accessibility	Zoom	Descriptions of the accessibility features available through Zoom	https://explore.zoom.us/en/accessibility

6. REFERENCES

6.1. POLICY

- Al-Muwil, A., Weerakkody, V., El-haddadeh, R., & Dwivedi, Y. (2019). Balancing Digital-By-Default with Inclusion: A Study of the Factors Influencing E-Inclusion in the UK. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 21(3), 635–659. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10796-019-09914-0>
- Babin, L. A., & Kopp, J. (2020). ADA Website Accessibility: What Businesses Need to Know. *Journal of Management Policy and Practice*, 21(3), 99–107. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/ada-website-accessibility-what-businesses-need/docview/2454439443/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Ballantyne, M., Jha, A., Jacobsen, A., Scott Hawker, J., & El-Glaly, Y. N. (2018). Study of accessibility guidelines of mobile applications. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 305–315. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3282894.3282921>
- Barricelli, B. R., Casiraghi, E., Dattolo, A., & Rizzi, A. (2021). 15 Years of Stanca Act: Are Italian Public universities websites accessible? *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 20(1), 185–200. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-020-00711-0>
- Chadwick, D., Wesson, C., & Fullwood, C. (2013). Internet Access by People with Intellectual Disabilities: Inequalities and Opportunities. *Future Internet*, 5(3), 376–397. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/fi5030376>

- Cooper, M. (2016). Web accessibility guidelines for the 2020s. *W4A 2016 - 13th Web for All Conference*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2899475.2899492>
- Dattolo, A., & Luccio, F. L. (2017). Accessible and Usable Websites and Mobile Applications for People with Autism Spectrum Disorders: a Comparative Study. *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Ambient Systems*, 4(13). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.17-5-2017.152549>
- De Lara, S. M. A., Watanabe, W. M., Dos Santos, E. P. B., & Fortes, R. P. M. (2010). Improving WCAG for elderly Web accessibility. *SIGDOC 2010 - Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Design of Communication*, 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1878450.1878480>
- Dearnley, C., Elliott, J., Hargreaves, J., Morris, S., Walker, L., Walker, S., & Arnold, C. (2010). Disabled people, effective practitioners: Enabling a health care workforce that better reflects society. *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences*, 5(8), 259–274. <https://doi.org/10.18848/1833-1882/cgp/v05i08/51835>
- Easton, C. (2011). The web content accessibility guidelines 2.0: An analysis of industry self-regulation. *International Journal of Law and Information Technology*, 19(1), 74–93. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijlit/eaq015>
- Ekstrand, V. S. (2017). Democratic governance, self-fulfillment and disability: Web accessibility under the americans with disabilities act and the first amendment. *Communication Law and Policy*, 22(4), 427–457. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10811680.2017.1364918>
- Else, S. (2008). Courts Must Welcome the Reality of the Modern World: Cyberspace Is a Place Under Title III of the Americans with Disabilities Act. *Washington and Lee Law Review*, 65(3), 1121–1158. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/courts-must-welcome-reality-modern-world/docview/613751786/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Ender, K. E., Kinney, B. J., Penrod, W. M., Bauder, D. K., & Simmons, T. (2007). Achieving Systemic Change with Universal Design for Learning and Digital Content. *Assistive Technology Outcomes & Benefits*, 4(1), 115–129. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/achieving-systemic-change-with-universal-design/docview/2067209324/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Erickson, W., Trerise, S., Lee, C., VanLooy, S., Knowlton, S., & Bruyère, S. (2013). The Accessibility and Usability of College Websites: Is your Website Presenting Barriers to Potential Students? *Community College Journal of Research and Practice*, 37(11), 864. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/accessibility-usability-college-websites-is-your/docview/1437226451/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Ferri, D., & Favalli, S. (2018). Web Accessibility for People with Disabilities in the European Union: Paving the Road to Social Inclusion. *Societies*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/soc8020040>

- Fielden, K., & Malcolm, P. (2009). Local E-government in New Zealand: Digital strategy, social inclusion and liveability. *53rd Annual Conference of the International Society for the Systems Sciences 2009: Making Liveable, Sustainable Systems Unremarkable*, 2, 941–957. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84865657914&partnerID=40&md5=f5a1c13326185c287e09081d0b03e8c6>
- Geiger, B., Evans, R. R., Cellitti, M. A., Smith, K. H., O’Neal, M. R., Firsing III, S. L., & Chandan, P. (2011). The Healthy Web--Access to Online Health Information for Individuals with Disabilities. *International Electronic Journal of Health Education*, 14, 93–100. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/healthy-web-access-online-health-information/docview/964178765/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Giannoumi, G. A., Land, M., Beyene, W. M., & Blanck, P. (2017). Web accessibility and technology protection measures: Harmonizing the rights of persons with cognitive disabilities and copyright protections on the web. *CYBERPSYCHOLOGY-JOURNAL OF PSYCHOSOCIAL RESEARCH ON CYBERSPACE*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.5817/CP2017-1-5>
- Giannoumis, G. A. (2014). Regulating web content: The nexus of legislation and performance standards in the United Kingdom and Norway. *Behavioral Sciences and the Law*, 32(1), 52–75. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsl.2103>
- Goggin, G., Ellis, K., & Hawkins, W. (2019). Disability at the centre of digital inclusion: assessing a new moment in technology and rights. *Communication Research and Practice*, 5(3), 290–303. <https://doi.org/10.1080/22041451.2019.1641061>
- Goggin, G., Hollier, S., & Hawkins, W. (2017). Internet accessibility and disability policy: Lessons for digital inclusion and equality from australia. *Internet Policy Review*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.14763/2017.1.452>
- Gonçalves, R., Martins, J., Branco, F., & Barroso, J. (2013). Web accessibility - From the evaluation and analysis to the implementation - The anoGov/PEPPOL case. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics): Vol. 8010 LNCS* (Issue PART 2, pp. 664–673). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-39191-0_71
- Jaeger, P. T., & Xie, B. (2009). Developing Online Community Accessibility Guidelines for Persons With Disabilities and Older Adults. *Journal of Disability Policy Studies*, 20(1), 55–63. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1044207308325997>
- James, A., Draffan, E. A., & Wald, M. (2017). Designing Web-Apps for All: How Do We Include Those with Cognitive Disabilities? In *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* (Vol. 242, pp. 665–668). <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-798-6-665>
- Kelly, B., Hassell, J., Sloan, D., Lukes, D., Draffan, E. A., & Lewthwaite, S. (2013). Bring Your Own Policy: Why Accessibility Standards Need to Be Contextually Sensitive. *Ariadne*, 71. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly->

journals/bring-your-own-policy-why-accessibility-standards/docview/1680141244/se-2?accountid=10457

- Kent, M., & Ellis, K. (2015). People with disability and new disaster communications: access and the social media mash-up. *Disability and Society*, 30(3), 419–431. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2015.1021756>
- Kim, H. K., & Park, J. (2020). Examination of the Protection Offered by Current Accessibility Acts and Guidelines to People with Disabilities in Using Information Technology Devices. *Electronics*, 9(5), 742. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/electronics9050742>
- Kous, K., Kuhar, S., Pavlinek, M., Heričko, M., & Pušnik, M. (2020). Web accessibility investigation of Slovenian municipalities' websites before and after the adoption of European Standard EN 301 549. *Universal Access in the Information Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-020-00732-9>
- Lazar, J., & Hochheiser, H. (2013). Legal aspects of interface accessibility in the U.S. *Communications of the ACM*, 56(12), 74–80. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2500498>
- Lewthwaite, S. (2014). Web accessibility standards and disability: Developing critical perspectives on accessibility. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, 36(16), 1375–1383. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638288.2014.938178>
- Loiacono, E. T., & Djamasbi, S. (2013). Corporate website accessibility: Does legislation matter? *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 12(1), 115–124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-011-0269-1>
- Moroney, J. (2021). REVIVING NEGOTIATED RULEMAKING FOR AN ACCESSIBLE INTERNET. *Michigan Law Review*, 119(7), 1581–1611. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/reviving-negotiated-rulemaking-accessible/docview/2539313576/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Moulin, C., & Sbodio, M. L. (2010). Improving the accessibility and efficiency of e-Government processes. *Proceedings of the 9th IEEE International Conference on Cognitive Informatics, ICCI 2010*, 603–610. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COGINF.2010.5599835>
- Muchagata, J., & Ferreira, A. (2019). Mobile apps for people with dementia: Are they compliant with the general data protection regulation (GDPR)? *HEALTHINF 2019 - 12th International Conference on Health Informatics, Proceedings; Part of 12th International Joint Conference on Biomedical Engineering Systems and Technologies, BIOSTEC 2019*, 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0007352200680077>
- Peters, C., & Bradbard, D. A. (2010). Web accessibility: an introduction and ethical implications. *Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society*, 8(2), 206–232. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/14779961011041757>
- Raymaker, D. M., Kapp, S. K., McDonald, K. E., Weiner, M., Ashkenazy, E., & Nicolaidis, C. (2019). Development of the AASPIRE Web Accessibility Guidelines for Autistic Web Users. *Autism in*

Adulthood : Challenges and Management, 1(2), 146–157.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1089/aut.2018.0020>

Reid, B. E. (2020). Internet architecture and disability. *Indiana Law Journal*, 95(2), 591–647.
<https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85095884607&partnerID=40&md5=94a367e829741c4d0f123fffb282b7d>

Rosenfeld, L., Torous, J., & Vahia, I. V. (2017). Data security and privacy in apps for dementia: An analysis of existing privacy policies. *The American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 25(8), 873–877. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jagp.2017.04.009>

Ruikai, D. (2021). INFORMATION ACCESSIBILITY FOR PUBLIC HEALTH EMERGENCIES-A CASE STUDY OF INFORMATION ACCESSIBILITY DURING THE NEW CORONAVIRUS OUTBREAK. *Frontiers of Law in China*, 16(1), 58–78. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3868/s050-010-021-0004-3>

Siebra, C., Gouveia, T., Filho, A., Correia, W., Penha, M., Anjos, M., Florentin, F., Silva, F. Q. B., & Santos, A. L. M. (2015). Usability for accessibility - A consolidation of requirements for mobile applications. *ASSETS 2015 - Proceedings of the 17th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*, 321–322. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2700648.2811358>

Sorger, D. (2018). WRITING THE ACCESS CODE: ENFORCING COMMERCIAL WEB ACCESSIBILITY WITHOUT REGULATIONS UNDER TITLE III OF THE AMERICANS WITH DISABILITIES ACT. *Boston College. Law School. Boston College Law Review*, 59(3), 1121–1152. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/writing-access-code-enforcing-commercial-web/docview/2032439265/se-2?accountid=10457>

Timmers, P. (2008). EU e-inclusion policy in context. *Info : The Journal of Policy, Regulation and Strategy for Telecommunications, Information and Media*, 10(5/6), 12–19. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/14636690810904670>

Trevisan, F., & Cogburn, D. L. (2020). Technology and accessibility in global governance and human rights: the experience of disability rights advocates. *Journal of Information, Communication & Ethics in Society*, 18(3), 377–391. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/JICES-02-2020-0016>

Viana, G. T., Maciel, C., De Arruda, N. A., & De Souza, P. C. (2017). Web accessibility guidelines and social networks: a systematic literature review . *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2039, 70–81. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85041381641&partnerID=40&md5=6fc160a5722935d7edc12ea94a5a34cf>

Wentz, B., Lazar, J., Stein, M., Gbenro, O., Holandez, E., & Ramsey, A. (2014). Danger, danger! Evaluating the accessibility of Web-based emergency alert sign-ups in the northeastern United States. *Government Information Quarterly*, 31(3), 488–497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2014.02.010>

Zhang, M., Chow, A., & Smith, H. (2020). COVID-19 contact-tracing apps: Analysis of the readability of privacy policies. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 22(12). <https://doi.org/10.2196/21572>

6.2. STUDIES

Ajrun, N. (2021). Bridging the Digital Divide Affecting Persons with Disabilities in Malaysia. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1034912X.2021.1901860>

Alonso-Virgos, L., Baena, L. R., & Crespo, R. G. (2020). Web accessibility and usability evaluation methodology for people with Down syndrome. *Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies, CISTI, 2020-June*. <https://doi.org/10.23919/CISTI49556.2020.9140858>

Andreasen, D. L., & Kanstrup, A. M. (2019). Digital relations among youth with cognitive disabilities: A field study of technology use for developing and maintaining social relations. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 250–254. https://doi.org/10.1145/3328_320.3328394

Arbelaitz, O., Martínez-Otzeta, J. M., & Muguerza, J. (2016). User modeling in a social network for cognitively disabled people. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 67(2), 305–317. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23381>

Arief, M., Rissanen, S., & Saranto, K. (2020). Effectiveness of web accessibility policy implementation in online healthcare information. In *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* (Vol. 270, pp. 1108–1112). <https://doi.org/10.3233/SHTI200334>

Bagga-Gupta, S., Dahlberg, G. M., & Winther, Y. (2016). Disabling and Enabling Technologies for Learning in Higher Education for All: Issues and Challenges for Whom? *Informatics*, 3(4), 21. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/informatics3040021>

Balasuriya, S. S., Sitbon, L., Zhang, J., & Anuar, K. (2021). Summary and Prejudice: Online Reading Preferences of Users with Intellectual Disability. *CHIIR 2021 - Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Human Information Interaction and Retrieval*, 285–289. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3406522.3446039>

Beaton, M. D., Hadly, G., & Babul, S. (2021). Stakeholder Recommendations to Increase the Accessibility of Online Health Information for Adults Experiencing Concussion Symptoms. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2020.557814>

Beentjes, K. M., Neal, D. P., Kerkhof, Y. J. F., Broeder, C., Moeridjan, Z. D. J., Ettema, T. P., Pelkmans, W., Muller, M. M., Graff, M. J. L., & Dröes, R.-M. (2020). Impact of the FindMyApps program on people with mild cognitive impairment or dementia and their caregivers; an exploratory pilot randomised controlled trial. *Disability and Rehabilitation. Assistive Technology*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2020.1842918>

- Benda, P., & Smejkalová, M. (2015). Web Interface for Education of Mentally Disabled Persons for Work in Horticulture. *AGRIS On-Line Papers in Economics and Informatics*, 7(1), 13–19. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/web-interface-education-mentally-disabled-persons/docview/1676112032/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Berget, G., & MacFarlane, A. (2020). What Is Known About the Impact of Impairments on Information Seeking and Searching? *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 71(5), 596–611. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24256>
- Berget, G., Mulvey, F., & Sandnes, F. E. (2016). Is visual content in textual search interfaces beneficial to dyslexic users? *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 92–93, 17–29. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2016.04.006>
- Berton, R., Gaggi, O., Kolasinska, A., Palazzi, C. E., & Quadrio, G. (2020). Are CAPTCHAs preventing robotic intrusion or accessibility for impaired users? *2020 IEEE 17th Annual Consumer Communications and Networking Conference, CCNC 2020*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCNC46108.2020.9045468>
- Brunskill, A. (2020). “Without that detail, i’m not coming”: The perspectives of students with disabilities on accessibility information provided on academic library websites. *College and Research Libraries*, 81(5), 768–788. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.81.5.768>
- Cajola, L. C. (2020). Inclusive e-learning and student with specific learning disorders at Roma tre university: Research data and development perspective . *Journal of Educational, Cultural and Psychological Studies*, 2020(21), 301–324. <https://doi.org/10.7358/ecps-2020-021-chia>
- Caria, S., Paternò, F., Santoro, C., & Semucci, V. (2018). The Design of Web Games for Helping Young High-Functioning Autistics in Learning How to Manage Money. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 23(6), 1735–1748. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11036-018-1069-0>
- Chen, C. J., Keong, M. W. Y., Teh, C. S., & Chuah, K. M. (2015). Learners with Dyslexia: Exploring Their Experiences with Different Online Reading Affordances. *Themes in Science and Technology Education*, 8(1), 63–79. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/learners-with-dyslexia-exploring-their/docview/1895985208/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Chen, J. V., Thi Le, H., & Tran, S. T. T. (2021). Understanding automated conversational agent as a decision aid_ matching agent’s conversation with customer’s shopping task. *Internet Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-11-2019-0447>
- Cho, M., & Kim, K. M. (2021). Exploring the disparity in tangible outcomes of internet use between persons with disabilities and persons without disabilities in South Korea. *Disability and Health Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dhjo.2021.101101>
- Craven, J., & Nietzio, A. (2007). A task-based approach to assessing the accessibility of web sites. *Performance Measurement and Metrics*, 8(2), 98–109. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/14678040710760603>

- de Avelar, L. O., Rezende, G. C., & Freire, A. P. (2015). WebHelpDyslexia: A Browser Extension to Adapt Web Content for People With Dyslexia. In Velasco, C and Weber, G and Barroso, J and Mohamad, Y and Paredes, H (Ed.), *PROCEEDINGS OF THE 6TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENHANCING ACCESSIBILITY AND FIGHTING INFO-EXCLUSION* (Vol. 67, pp. 150–159). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.09.259>
- Díez-Palomar, J., Ocampo Castillo, M. D. S., Pascual, A. M., & Oliver, E. (2021). Adults With Special Educational Needs Participating in Interactive Learning Environments in Adult Education: Educational, Social, and Personal Improvements. A Case Study. *Frontiers in Psychology, 12*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.662867>
- Dolamore, S. (2021). Accessibility features in ZOOM to improve equity in the MPA classroom. *Journal of Public Affairs Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15236803.2021.1929020>
- Duplaga, M. (2017). Digital divide among people with disabilities: Analysis of data from a nationwide study for determinants of Internet use and activities performed online. *PLoS One, 12*(6). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0179825>
- Edler, C., & Rath, M. (2014). People with learning disabilities using the ipad as a communication tool - Conditions and impact with regard to e-inclusion. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics): Vol. 8547 LNCS* (Issue PART 1, pp. 177–180). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-08596-8_27
- Ellis, K. (2011). Embracing learners with disability: Web 2.0, access and insight. *Telecommunications Journal of Australia, 61*(2). <https://doi.org/10.7790/tja.v61i2.199>
- Eraslan, S., Yaneva, V., Yesilada, Y., & Harper, S. (2017). Do web users with autism experience barriers when searching for information within web pages? *Proceedings of the 14th Web for All Conference, W4A 2017*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3058555.3058566>
- Eraslan, S., Yaneva, V., Yesilada, Y., & Harper, S. (2019). Web users with autism: Eye tracking evidence for differences. *Behaviour & Information Technology, 38*(7), 678–700. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2018.1551933>
- Fernando, S., Money, A., Elliman, T., & Lines, L. (2010). Older adults and diffusion of assistive web-base technologies. *Journal of Information Technology Research, 3*(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jitr.2010010101>
- Fichten, C. S., Ferraro, V., Asuncion, J. V., Chwojka, C., Barile, M., Nguyen, M. N., Klomp, R., & Wolforth, J. (2009). Disabilities and e-Learning Problems and Solutions: An Exploratory Study. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society, 12*(4), 241–256. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/disabilities-e-learning-problems-solutions/docview/1287039126/se-2?accountid=10457>

- Fickas, S., Sohlberg, M., & Hung, P.-F. (2008). Route-following assistance for travelers with cognitive impairments: A comparison of four prompt modes. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 66(12), 876–888. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2008.07.006>
- Frogren, J., Quitana, M., Anderberg, P., Berglund, J. S., & Garolera, M. (2018). Designing a model app for older persons with cognitive impairment – insights from a usability perspective. *Gerontechnology*, 17. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/designing-model-app-older-persons-with-cognitive/docview/2110073272/se-2?accountid=10457>
- García, A. M., De Bra, P., Stash, N., Fletcher, G. H. L., Fabri, M., & Pechenizkiy, M. (2016). Adaptive web-based educational application for autistic students. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 1628. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84983646683&partnerID=40&md5=d2372ec25d6b7b13573afdece9d97623>
- Gillespie-Lynch, K., Kapp, S. K., Shane-Simpson, C., Smith, D. S., & Hutman, T. (2014). Intersections between the autism spectrum and the internet: Perceived benefits and preferred functions of computer-mediated communication. *Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities*, 52(6), 456–469. <https://doi.org/10.1352/1934-9556-52.6.456>
- Gomez, J., Torrado, J. C., & Montoro, G. (2017). Using Smartphones to Assist People with Down Syndrome in Their Labour Training and Integration: A Case Study. *Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing (Online)*, 2017, 15. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2017/5062371>
- Gregor, P., & Dickinson, A. (2007). Cognitive difficulties and access to information systems: An interaction design perspective. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 5(4), 393–400. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-006-0064-6>
- Grellmann, B., Neate, T., Roper, A., Wilson, S., & Marshall, J. (2018). Investigating mobile accessibility guidance for people with aphasia. *ASSETS 2018 - Proceedings of the 20th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*, 410–413. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3234695.3241011>
- Gupta, T., Sisodia, M., Fazulbhoy, S., Raju, M., & Agrawal, S. (2019). Improving Accessibility for Dyslexic Impairments using Augmented Reality. *2019 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics, ICCCI 2019*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCI.2019.8822152>
- Hahn, E. A., Downing, N. R., Stout, J. C., Paulsen, J. S., Ready, B., Goodnight, S., Lai, J.-S., Miner, J. A., & Carlozzi, N. E. (2018). Understanding the need for assistance with survey completion in people with Huntington disease. *Quality of Life Research*, 27(3), 801–810. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-017-1747-6>
- Hedman, A., Lindqvist, E., & Nygard, L. (2016). How older adults with mild cognitive impairment relate to technology as part of present and future everyday life: a qualitative study. *BMC Geriatrics*, 16. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12877-016-0245-y>

- Heyn, P. C., Goldberg, A., McGrew, G., & Bodine, C. (2021). The effects of a mobile-based vocational skill building coaching technology intervention for people with cognitive disabilities: A pilot feasibility study. *Journal of Rehabilitation and Assistive Technologies Engineering*, 8, 20556683211009732. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/20556683211009731>
- Hill, D. A., Belcher, L., Brigman, H. E., Renner, S., & Stephens, B. (2013). The Apple iPad™ as an innovative employment support for young adults with autism spectrum disorder and other developmental disabilities. *Journal of Applied Rehabilitation Counseling*, 44(1), 28–37. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/apple-ipad-™-as-innovative-employment-support/docview/1368591718/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Holz, H., & Meurers, D. (2021). Interaction Styles in Context: Comparing Drag-and-Drop, Point-and-Touch, and Touch in a Mobile Spelling Game. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 37(9), 835–850. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2020.1848160>
- Igo, L. B., Riccomini, P. J., Bruning, R. H., & Pope, G. G. (2006). How should middle-school students with LD approach online note taking? a mixed-methods study. *Learning Disability Quarterly*, 29(2), 89–100. <https://doi.org/10.2307/30035537>
- Iqbal, S., Irfan, M., Ahsan, K., Hussain, M. A., Awais, M., Shiraz, M., Hamdi, M., & Alghamdi, A. (2020). A novel mobile wallet model for elderly using fingerprint as authentication factor. *IEEE Access*, 8, 177405–177423. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3025429>
- Ismail, A., Kuppusamy, K. S., & Paiva, S. (2020). Accessibility analysis of higher education institution websites of Portugal. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 19(3), 685–700. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-019-00653-2>
- Joddrell, P., & Astell, A. J. (2019). Implementing Accessibility Settings in Touchscreen Apps for People Living with Dementia. *Gerontology*, 65(5), 560–570. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000498885>
- Joddrell, P., Hernandez, A., & Astell, A. J. (2016). Identifying existing, accessible touchscreen games for people living with dementia. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)* (Vol. 9758, pp. 509–514). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-41264-1_69
- Kagohara, D. M., van der Meer, L., Ramdoss, S., O'Reilly, M. F., Lancioni, G. E., Davis, T. N., Rispoli, M., Lang, R., Marschik, P. B., Sutherland, D., Green, V. A., & Sigafos, J. (2013). Using iPods® and iPads® in teaching programs for individuals with developmental disabilities: A systematic review. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 34(1), 147–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2012.07.027>
- Karreman, J., van der Geest, T., & Buursink, E. (2007). Accessible Website Content Guidelines for Users with Intellectual Disabilities. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 20(6), 510–518. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3148.2006.00353.x>

- Kennedy, H., Evans, S., & Thomas, S. (2011). Can the Web Be Made Accessible for People with Intellectual Disabilities? *The Information Society*, 27(1), 29–39. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/can-web-be-made-accessible-people-with/docview/870997570/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Kenyon, S. (2006). The “accessibility diary”: Discussing a new methodological approach to understand the impact of Internet use upon personal travel and activity participation. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 14(2), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2005.10.005>
- Kerkhof, Y. J. F., Bergsma, A., Mangiaracina, F., Planting, C. H. M., Graff, M. J. L., & Dröes, R. M. (2021). Are people with mild dementia able to (re)learn how to use technology? A literature review. *International Psychogeriatrics*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1041610221000016>
- Khanlou, N., Khan, A., Vazquez, L. M., Zangeneh, M., Nazilla, K., Attia, K., Vazquez, L. M., & Masood, Z. (2021). Digital Literacy, Access to Technology and Inclusion for Young Adults with Developmental Disabilities. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 33(1), 1–25. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10882-020-09738-w>
- Kim, J. Y., & Fienup, D. M. (2021). Increasing Access to Online Learning for Students With Disabilities During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Special Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022466921998067>
- Krivec, T., Košak Babuder, M., Godec, P., Weingerl, P., & Stankovič Elesini, U. (2020). Impact of digital text variables on legibility for persons with dyslexia. *Dyslexia*, 26(1), 87–103. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dys.1646>
- Kvikne, B., & Berget, G. (2021). In search of trustworthy information: a qualitative study of the search behavior of people with dyslexia in Norway. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-019-00703-9>
- Kwan, R. Y. C., Cheung, D. S. K., & Kor, P. P.-K. (2020). The use of smartphones for wayfinding by people with mild dementia. *Dementia*, 19(3), 721–735. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1471301218785461>
- Lancioni, G. E., Singh, N. N., O’Reilly, M. F., Sigafos, J., Boccasini, A., Alberti, G., & Lang, R. (2014). People with Multiple Disabilities Use Basic Reminding Technology to Engage in Daily Activities at the Appropriate Times. *Journal of Developmental and Physical Disabilities*, 26(3), 347–355. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10882-014-9373-5>
- Larco, A., Carrillo, J., Chicaiza, N., Yanez, C., & Luján-Mora, S. (2021). Moving beyond Limitations: Designing the Helpdys App for Children with Dyslexia in Rural Areas. *Sustainability*, 13(13), 7081. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/su13137081>
- Lazar, J., Woglom, C., Chung, J., Schwartz, A., Hsieh, Y. G., Moore, R., Crowley, D., & Skotko, B. (2018). Co-Design Process of a Smart Phone App to Help People With Down Syndrome Manage Their Nutritional Habits. *JOURNAL OF USABILITY STUDIES*, 13(2), 73–93.

- Lim, C., Song, H.-D., & Lee, Y. (2012). Improving the usability of the user interface for a digital textbook platform for elementary-school students. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, *60*(1), 159–173. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-011-9222-5>
- Lindsay, S., Kosareva, P., Sukhai, M., Thomson, N., & Stinson, J. (2021). Online Self-Determination Toolkit for Youth With Disabilities: Protocol for a Mixed Methods Evaluation Study. *JMIR Research Protocols*, *10*(1). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2196/20463>
- Livingstone-Lee, S. A., Skelton, R. W., & Livingston, N. (2014). Transit apps for people with brain injury and other cognitive disabilities: The state of the art. *Assistive Technology : The Official Journal of RESNA*, *26*(4), 209–218. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10400435.2014.930076>
- Lloyd, G., Munro, S. D., & Arnott, J. L. (2017). Mobile Delivery of Health Information for People with Mild Cognitive Impairment. In Cudd, P and DeWitte, L (Ed.), *HARNESSING THE POWER OF TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE LIVES* (Vol. 242, pp. 31–37). <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-798-6-31>
- MacFarlane, A., Albrair, A., Jones, S. A., Al-Wabil, A., & Zaphiris, P. (2010). The effect of dyslexia on information retrieval: A pilot study. *Journal of Documentation*, *66*(3), 307–326. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00220411011038421>
- Mak, B., Beckman, P., & Bohn, N. (2013). Mobile phone accessibility values for users with disabilities. *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, *11*(3), 245–261. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMC.2013.055335>
- Malinowsky, C., Almkvist, O., Kottorp, A., Nygård, L., & Nygard, L. (2010). Ability to manage everyday technology: a comparison of persons with dementia or mild cognitive impairment and older adults without cognitive impairment. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Technology*, *5*(6), 462–469. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3109/17483107.2010.496098>
- Malinowsky, C., Nygard, L., Kottorp, A., Nygård, L., Kottorp, A., Nygard, L., Kottorp, A., Nygård, L., & Kottorp, A. (2014). Using a screening tool to evaluate potential use of e-health services for older people with and without cognitive impairment. *Aging & Mental Health*, *18*(3), 340–345. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13607863.2013.832731>
- McCarron, H. R., Zmora, R., & Gaugler, J. E. (2019). A web-based mobile app with a smartwatch to support social engagement in persons with memory loss: Pilot randomized controlled trial. *JMIR Aging*, *2*(1). <https://doi.org/10.2196/13378>
- Mehrvarz, M., Heidari, E., Farrokhnia, M., & Noroozi, O. (2021). The mediating role of digital informal learning in the relationship between students' digital competency and their academic performance. *Computers and Education*, *167*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2021.104184>
- Melo, A. M., & Baranauskas, M. C. C. (2006). An inclusive approach to cooperative evaluation of web user interfaces. *ICEIS 2006 - 8th International Conference on Enterprise Information Systems*,

Proceedings, HCI, 65–70. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-47249153486&partnerID=40&md5=61369ba0381afffd604f8854878da557>

- Menger, F., Morris, J., & Salis, C. (2017). Internet Use in Aphasia: A Case Study Viewed Through the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health. *Topics in Language Disorders*, 37(1), 6–24. <https://doi.org/10.1097/TLD.000000000000110>
- Moisey, S., & van de Keere, R. (2007). Inclusion and the Internet: Teaching adults with developmental disabilities to use information and communication technology. *Developmental Disabilities Bulletin*, 35(1–2), 72–102. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/inclusion-internet-teaching-adults-with/docview/622017137/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Moreno, F., Coret, J., Jiménez, E., Márquez, S., & Alcantud, F. (2012). Evaluation of web browsing experience by people with cognitive disability. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2379636.2379673>
- Morris, M. R., Fourney, A., Ali, A., & Vonessen, L. (2018). Understanding the needs of searchers with dyslexia. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings, 2018-April*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3173574.3173609>
- Nelson Bryen, D., Carey, A., & Friedman, M. (2007). Cell phone use by adults with intellectual disabilities. *INTELLECTUAL AND DEVELOPMENTAL DISABILITIES*, 45(1), 1–9. [https://doi.org/10.1352/1934-9556\(2007\)45\[1:CPUBAW\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1352/1934-9556(2007)45[1:CPUBAW]2.0.CO;2)
- Ngubane-Mokiwa, S. A., & Zongozzi, J. N. (2021). Exclusion Reloaded: The Chronicles of Covid-19 on Students with Disabilities in a South African Open Distance Learning Context. *Journal of Intellectual Disability - Diagnosis and Treatment*, 9(1), 137–147. <https://doi.org/10.6000/2292-2598.2021.09.01.17>
- Oksnebjerg, L., Woods, B., Ruth, K., Lauridsen, A., Kristiansen, S., Hoist, H. D., & Waldemar, G. (2020). A Tablet App Supporting Self-Management for People With Dementia: Explorative Study of Adoption and Use Patterns. *JMIR MHEALTH AND UHEALTH*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.2196/14694>
- Ophoff, J., Johnson, G., & Renaud, K. (2021). Cognitive function vs accessible authentication: Insights from dyslexia research. *Proceedings of the 18th International Web for All Conference, W4A 2021*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3430263.3452427>
- Passerino, L. M., & Santarosa, L. C. M. (2007). Social interaction in Austim in learning virtual environment . *Psicologia: Reflexao e Critica*, 20(1), 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1590/s0102-79722007000100008>
- Pawlowska, J., Nielek, R., & Wierzbicki, A. (2019). Lost in Online Stores? Agent-Based Modeling of Cognitive Limitations of Elderly Online Consumers. In Thomson, R and Bisgin, H and Dancy, C and Hyder, A (Ed.), *SOCIAL, CULTURAL, AND BEHAVIORAL MODELING, SBP-BRIMS 2019* (Vol. 11549, pp. 204–213). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-21741-9_21

- Pereira, L. S., & Archambault, D. (2016). Understanding how people with cerebral palsy interact with the web 2.0. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)* (Vol. 9758, pp. 239–242). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-41264-1_32
- Persson, H., Ohlsson, K., Petersén, S., & Jonsäll, A. (2009). Unexploited resources in interaction design for universal access: People with impairments as a resource for interaction designers. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics): Vol. 5614 LNCS* (Issue PART 1, pp. 145–153). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-02707-9_16
- Poobrasert, O. (2009). Work in Progress: A Case Study of Usability Testing of Software Tools for People with Learning Disabilities. In Mastorakis, N and Demiralp, M and Rudas, I and Bulucea, CA (Ed.), *EDUTE 2009: PROCEEDINGS OF THE 5TH WSEAS/IASME INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES* (pp. 157–161).
- Powell, L., Parker, J., Robertson, N., & Harpin, V. (2017). Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: Is There an App for That? Suitability Assessment of Apps for Children and Young People With ADHD. *JMIR MHealth and UHealth*, 5(10). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2196/mhealth.7371>
- Rao, K., Torres, C., & Smith, S. J. (2021). Digital Tools and UDL-Based Instructional Strategies to Support Students With Disabilities Online. *Journal of Special Education Technology*, 36(2), 105–112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162643421998327>
- Rello, L., Bayarri, C., & Görriz, A. (2013). Dyslexia exercises on my tablet are more fun. *W4A 2013 - International Cross-Disciplinary Conference on Web Accessibility*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2461121.2461148>
- Renaud, K. (2021). Accessible cyber security: The next frontier? *ICISSP 2021 - Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy*, 9–18. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85102991777&partnerID=40&md5=b8479b1c5b01115319d93d0ddaf5e48c>
- Renaud, K., Johnson, G., & Ophoff, J. (2020). Dyslexia and Password Usage: Accessibility in Authentication Design. In *IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology: Vol. 593 IFIPAI* (pp. 259–268). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-57404-8_20
- Rivas-Costa, C., Anido-Rifón, L., Fernández-Iglesias, M. J., Gómez-Carballa, M. A., Valladares-Rodríguez, S., & Soto-Barreiros, R. (2014). An Accessible Platform for People With Disabilities. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 30(6), 480–494. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2014.888503>
- Rocha, T., Martins, J., Goncalves, R., & Branco, F. (2016). Usability evaluation of an entertainment platform by people with intellectual disabilities . *Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies, CISTI, 2016-July*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CISTI.2016.7521507>

- Rocha, T. T., Bessa, M., Gonçalves, M., Cabral, L., Godinho, F., Peres, E., Reis, M. C., Magalhães, L., Chalmers, A., Goncalves, M., Cabral, L., Godinho, F., Peres, E., Reis, M. C., Magalhaes, L., & Chalmers, A. (2012). The recognition of web pages' hyperlinks by people with intellectual disabilities: An evaluation study. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 25(6), 542–552. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-3148.2012.00700.x>
- Rotondi, A. J., Spring, M. R., Hanusa, B. H., Eack, S. M., & Haas, G. L. (2017). Designing eHealth Applications to Reduce Cognitive Effort for Persons With Severe Mental Illness: Page Complexity, Navigation Simplicity, and Comprehensibility. *JMIR Human Factors*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.2196/humanfactors.6221>
- Rupprecht, D., Blum, R., & Bomsdorf, B. (2014). User centered inclusive design for people with dyslexia: Experiences from a project on accessibility. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)* (Vol. 8742, pp. 307–314). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-44811-3_23
- Samboma, T. A. (2021). Leaving no one behind: Intellectual disability during COVID-19 in Africa. *International Social Work*, 64(2), 265–269. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020872820967413>
- Santhanam, N. (2012). Wii remote as a web navigation device for people with cerebral palsy. *ASSETS'12 - Proceedings of the 14th International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility*, 303–304. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2384916.2385005>
- Sapp, W. (2009). Universal Design: Online Educational Media for Students with Disabilities. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness*, 103(8), 495–500. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/universal-design-online-educational-media/docview/61853066/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Savidis, A., Grammenos, D., & Stephanidis, C. (2006). Developing inclusive e-learning systems. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 5(1), 51–72. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-006-0024-1>
- Scott, R., Collins, B., Knight, V., & Kleinert, H. (2013). Teaching Adults with Moderate Intellectual Disability ATM Use via the “iPod.” *Education and Training in Autism and Developmental Disabilities*, 48(2), 190–199. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/teaching-adults-with-moderate-intellectual/docview/1651843749/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Shonfeld, M., & Ronen, I. (2006). Online Learning: Bright Spots for Students with Learning Disabilities. In *Proceedings of the Second IASTED International Conference on Education and Technology*. Acta Press Inc , #80, 4500-16 Avenue N.W , Calgary, AB, T3B 0M6, Canada, [mailto:comments@actapress.com], [URL:http://www.actapress.com/Abstract.aspx?paperId=27558http://www.actapress.com]. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/conference-papers->

proceedings/online-learning-bright-spots-students-with/docview/29417182/se-2?accountid=10457

- Sidek, R. M., Noraziah, A., Wahab, M. H. A., & Idrus, S. Z. S. (2021). An Observation of Usability Website for Down Syndrome Children. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1793(1). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1793/1/012029>
- Sillanpaa, N., Alli, S., & Overmark, T. (2011). Easy-To-Use Social Network Service for People with Cognitive or Speech and Language Impairments. In Gelderblom, GJ and Soede, M and Adriaens, L and Miesenberger, K (Ed.), *EVERYDAY TECHNOLOGY FOR INDEPENDENCE AND CARE* (Vol. 29, pp. 913–919). <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-60750-814-4-913>
- South, L., Safo, D., & Borkin, M. A. (2021). Detecting and defending against seizure-inducing gifs in social media. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3411764.3445510>
- Spaniol, M., Klamma, R., Springer, L., & Jarke, M. (2006). Aphasic communities of learning on the web. *International Journal of Distance Education Technologies*, 4(1), 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jdet.2006010103>
- Talib, R., Sunar, M., & Mohamed, R. (2020). Digital Society and Economy for People with Disabilities in Industry 4.0 : Malaysia Perspectives. *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Creative Technologies*, 6(20). <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.30-7-2019.162949>
- Teixeira, P., Eusébio, C., & Teixeira, L. (2021). How diverse is hotel website accessibility? A study in the central region of Portugal using web diagnostic tools. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14673584211022797>
- Thompson, K. M., & Copeland, C. (2020). Inclusive considerations for optimal online learning in times of disasters and crises. *Information and Learning Science*, 121(7/8), 481–486. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/ILS-04-2020-0083>
- Volkova, I. P., Koroleva, N. N., Bogdanovskaya, I. M., Ikonnikova, G. Y., & Mashkova, A. V. (2019). Problematic internet usage by adolescents with disabilities. *Obrazovanie i Nauka*, 21(9), 98–121. <https://doi.org/10.17853/1994-5639-2019-9-98-121>
- Vollenwyder, B., Opwis, K., & Brühlmann, F. (2020). How web professionals perceive web accessibility in practice: Active roles, process phases and key disabilities. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics): Vol. 12376 LNCS* (pp. 294–302). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-58796-3_35
- Wallcook, S., Nygård, L., Kottorp, A., & Malinowsky, C. (2019). The use of everyday information communication technologies in the lives of older adults living with and without dementia in Sweden. *Assistive Technology: The Official Journal of RESNA*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10400435.2019.1644685>

- Wentz, B., Pham, D., Feaser, E., Smith, D., Smith, J., & Wilson, A. (2019). Documenting the accessibility of 100 US bank and finance websites. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 18(4), 871–880. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-018-0616-6>
- Williams, P. (2013). Web site usability testing involving people with learning disabilities using only images and audio to access information. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 13(2), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-3802.2012.01235.x>
- Williams, P. (2006). Developing methods to evaluate web usability with people with learning difficulties. *British Journal of Special Education*, 33(4), 173–179. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8578.2006.00436.x>
- Williams, P. (2017). Eliciting web site preferences of people with learning disabilities. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 17(1), 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1471-3802.12099>
- Williams, P., & Cendón, B. V. (2020). Smartphones and people with intellectual disabilities: An international comparison of contextual social barriers for effective usage. *IMCIC 2020 - 11th International Multi-Conference on Complexity, Informatics and Cybernetics, Proceedings, 1*, 25–30. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85085942887&partnerID=40&md5=c4a046f96c1c57023a21dfda6971ba5b>
- Williams, P., & Hennig, C. (2015). Effect of web page menu orientation on retrieving information by people with learning disabilities. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 66(4), 674–683. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23214>
- Wu, S., Reynolds, L., Li, X., & Guzmán, F. (2019). Design and evaluation of a social media writing support tool for people with dyslexia. *Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300746>
- Yaneva, V., Ha, L. A., Eraslan, S., & Yesilada, Y. (2019). Adults with high-functioning autism process web pages with similar accuracy but higher cognitive effort compared to controls. *Proceedings of the 16th Web For All 2019 Personalization - Personalizing the Web, W4A 2019*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3315002.3317563>
- Zaagsma, M., Volkers, K. M., Swart, E. A. K., Schippers, A. P., & Van Hove, G. (2020). The use of online support by people with intellectual disabilities living independently during COVID-19. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, 64(10), 750–756. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jir.12770>
- Zaphiris, P., Kurniawan, S., & Ghiawadwala, M. (2007). A systematic approach to the development of research-based web design guidelines for older people. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, 6(1), 59–75. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-006-0054-8>
- Zhang, X., Tlili, A., Nascimbeni, F., Burgos, D., Huang, R., Ting-Wen, C., Jemni, M., & Khribi, M. K. (2020). Accessibility within open educational resources and practices for disabled learners: a systematic literature review. *Smart Learning Environments*, 7(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40561-019-0113-2>

- Zhu, R., Hardy, D., & Myers, T. (2019). Co-designing with adolescents with autism spectrum disorder: From ideation to implementation. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 106–116. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3369457.3370914>
- Zubair, M. S., Brown, D., Hughes-Roberts, T., & Bates, M. (2018). Evaluating the accessibility of scratch for children with cognitive impairments. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*: Vol. 10907 LNCS (pp. 660–676). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92049-8_49

6.3. TOOLS

- Alsaeedi, A. (2020). Comparing Web Accessibility Evaluation Tools and Evaluating the Accessibility of Webpages: Proposed Frameworks. *Information*, 11(1), 40. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/info11010040>
- Avelar, L. O. D., Rezende, G. C., & Freire, A. P. (2015). WebHelpDyslexia: A Browser Extension to Adapt Web Content for People with Dyslexia. *Procedia Computer Science*, 67, 150–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2015.09.259>
- Bai, A., Fuglerud, K., Skjerve, R. A., & Halbach, T. (2018). Categorization and comparison of accessibility testing methods for software development. In *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics* (Vol. 256, pp. 821–831). <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-923-2-821>
- Berton, R., Kolasinska, A., Gaggi, O., Palazzi, C. E., & Quadrio, G. (2020). A Chrome extension to help people with dyslexia. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3399715.3399843>
- Bozkurt, A., Bozkurt, S. S., Caliskan, H., Guler, E., Dincer, G. D., & Sezgin, S. (2015). DESIGN CRITERIA FOR INTERACTIVE E-BOOKS AND INTERACTIVE CONTENT BASED TEACHING APPS FOR LEARNERS WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER. In Chova, LG and Martinez, AL and Torres, IC (Ed.), *ICERI2015: 8TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF EDUCATION, RESEARCH AND INNOVATION* (pp. 3214–3221).
- Bozza, A., Mesiti, M., Valtolina, S., Dini, S., & Ribaudò, M. (2010). Accessibility and usability of a collaborative e-learning application. *CSEDU 2010 - 2nd International Conference on Computer Supported Education, Proceedings*, 1, 102–109. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-77956323377&partnerID=40&md5=4de00ae969f5e026dfd609bfc547c6b8>
- Brunvand, S., & Abadeh, H. (2010). Making online learning accessible: Using technology to declutter the web. *Intervention in School and Clinic*, 45(5), 304–311. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1053451209359075>
- Colman, J., & Gnanayutham, P. (2012). Accessible button interfaces: Improving accessibility for brain-injured and other disabled users. *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching Technologies*, 7(4), 40–52. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jwltd.2012100104>

- Ellis, K. (2010). A purposeful rebuilding: Youtube, representation, accessibility and the socio-political space of disability. *Telecommunications Journal of Australia*, 60(2), 21.1-21.12. <https://doi.org/10.2104/tja10021>
- Gaggi, O., & Pederiva, V. (2021). WCAG4All, a tool for making web accessibility rules accessible. *2021 IEEE 18th Annual Consumer Communications and Networking Conference, CCNC 2021*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CCNC49032.2021.9369484>
- Gulzar, M. M., Javed, M. Y., Rizvi, S. T. H., Rahman, M. H., & Tahir, M. S. (2019). Implementation of Windows Interface for Disabled Persons. *3rd International Conference on Innovative Computing, ICIC 2019*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIC48496.2019.8966742>
- Harrison, R., Flood, D., & Duce, D. (2013). Usability of mobile applications: literature review and rationale for a new usability model. *Journal of Interaction Science*, 1(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/2194-0827-1-1>
- Heron, M., Hanson, V. L., & Ricketts, I. (2013). Open source and accessibility: advantages and limitations. *Journal of Interaction Science*, 1(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/2194-0827-1-2>
- Hornung, H., & Baranauskas, M. C. C. (2011). Towards a design rationale for inclusive e-government services. *International Journal of Electronic Government Research*, 7(3), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.4018/jegr.2011070101>
- Ismail, A., & Kuppusamy, K. S. (2019). Web accessibility investigation and identification of major issues of higher education websites with statistical measures: A case study of college websites. *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2019.03.011>
- Janeth Lancheros-Cuesta, D., Carrillo-Ramos, A., & Pavlich-Mariscal, J. (2013). Personal Learning Environment for Disabled People. In Rocha, A and Reis, LP and Cota, MP and Painho, M and Neto, MC (Ed.), *PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2013 8TH IBERIAN CONFERENCE ON INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES (CISTI 2013)*.
- Larco, A., Enríquez, F., & Luján-Mora, S. (2018). IOS apps for people with intellectual disability: A quality assessment. *CSEDU 2018 - Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Computer Supported Education*, 2, 258–264. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0006778602580264>
- Lovell-Simons, A., & Kerr, S. (2011). E-books - a key to greater accessibility. *ASCILITE 2011 - The Australasian Society for Computers in Learning in Tertiary Education*, 826–828. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84870808535&partnerID=40&md5=3cd424562486d248a48699b7618b5652>
- Massengale, L. R., & Vasquez, E. (2016). Assessing Accessibility: Are Online Courses Better Than Face-to-Face Instruction At Providing Access to Course Content for Students with Disabilities? *Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 16(1), 69–79. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.14434/josotl.v16i1.19101>

- Matausch, K., Peböck, B., & Pühretmair, F. (2012). Accessible content generation an integral part of accessible web design. *Procedia Computer Science*, *14*, 274–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2012.10.031>
- McCarthy, J. E., & Swierenga, S. J. (2010). What we know about dyslexia and Web accessibility: A research review. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, *9*(2), 147–152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-009-0160-5>
- Michailidou, E., Eraslan, S., Yesilada, Y., & Harper, S. (2021). Automated prediction of visual complexity of web pages: Tools and evaluations. *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*, *145*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2020.102523>
- Money, A. G., Lines, L., Fernando, S., & Elliman, A. D. (2011). e-Government online forms: Design guidelines for older adults in Europe. *Universal Access in the Information Society*, *10*(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10209-010-0191-y>
- Nahon, K., Benbasat, I., & Grange, C. (2012). The missing link: Intention to produce online content accessible to people with disabilities by non-professionals. *Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 1747–1757. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2012.578>
- Nunez, O. H., Tabares-Morales, V., & Duque-Mendez, N. (2020). Web Accessibility Toolbar: Allyxe (Accessibility for Everyone) . *Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies, CISTI, 2020-June*. <https://doi.org/10.23919/CISTI49556.2020.9140928>
- Ojha, P. K., Ismail, A., & Kundumani Srinivasan, K. (2021). Perusal of readability with focus on web content understandability. *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences*, *33*(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksuci.2018.03.007>
- Pascual, A., Ribera, M., & Granollers, T. (2015). Comunicability of two web 2.0 accessibility evaluation tools . *2015 10th Colombian Computing Conference, 10CCC 2015*, 269–272. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ColumbianCC.2015.7333425>
- Pavlik, J. V. (2017). Experiential media and disabilities in education: Enabling learning through immersive, interactive, customizable, and multi-sensorial digital platforms. *Ubiquitous Learning*, *10*(1), 15–22. <https://doi.org/10.18848/1835-9795/CGP/v10i01/15-22>
- Piovesan, S. D., Wagner, R., Medina, R. D., & Passerino, L. M. (2013). Virtual Reality system to the inclusion of people with disabilities in the work market. *2013 12th International Conference on Information Technology Based Higher Education and Training, ITHET 2013*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ITHET.2013.6671021>
- Rello, L., Bayarri, C., Gòrriz, A., Baeza-Yates, R., Gupta, S., Kanvinde, G., Saggion, H., Bott, S., Carlini, R., & Topac, V. (2013). DysWebxia 2.0 More accessible text for people with dyslexia. *W4A 2013 - International Cross-Disciplinary Conference on Web Accessibility*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2461121.2461150>

- Roig-Vila, R., Ferrández, S., & Ferri-Miralles, I. (2014). Assessment of web content accessibility levels in Spanish official online education environments. *International Education Studies*, 7(6), 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v7n6p31>
- Rose, G. (2011). Assessable online discussions to support postgraduate student learning in transport planning. In *Transportation Research Record* (Issue 2211, pp. 36–43). <https://doi.org/10.3141/2211-05>
- Roth, K. (2013). Adapt with Apps. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 84(2), 4–6. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/adapt-with-apps/docview/1419745761/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Sik-Lanyi, C., & Orbán-Mihálykó, É. (2019). Accessibility Testing of European Health-Related Websites. *Arabian Journal for Science and Engineering*, 44(11), 9171–9190. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13369-019-04017-z>
- Skiada, R., Soroniati, E., Gardeli, A., & Zisis, D. (2014). EasyLexia 2.0: Redesigning Our Mobile Application for Children with Learning Difficulties. *Themes in Science and Technology Education*, 7(2), 119–135. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/easylexia-2-0-redesigning-our-mobile-application/docview/1895976027/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Solovieva, T. I., & Bock, J. M. (2014). Monitoring for Accessibility and University Websites: Meeting the Needs of People with Disabilities. *Journal of Postsecondary Education and Disability*, 27(2), 113–127. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/monitoring-accessibility-university-websites/docview/1651856804/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Talhi, S., Khadraoui, F., & Djoudi, M. (2012). Implementing WAI Authoring Tool Accessibility Guidelines in Developing Adaptive Elearning. *International Journal of Modern Education and Computer Science*, 4(9), 1–13. <https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/implementing-wai-authoring-tool-accessibility/docview/1627740678/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Tyler, N., & Wainstein, M. (2007). An accessible interface for a mobile phone-based travel information system. *New Trends in ICT and Accessibility - Proceedings of the 1st International Conference in Information and Communication Technology and Accessibility, ICTA 2007*, 39–42. <https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84880199590&partnerID=40&md5=442b56eb50cc1cf0cb06c34d65ab2a68>
- Watanabe, W. M., Neto, D. F., Bittar, T. J., & Fortes, R. P. M. (2010). WCAG conformance approach based on Model-Driven Development and WebML. *SIGDOC 2010 - Proceedings of the 28th ACM International Conference on Design of Communication*, 167–174. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1878450.1878479>

- WEBER-HOTTLEMAN, K. (2021). Using Personas for Accessible Design. *The Journal of Business Diversity*, 21(1), 90–94.
<https://login.udel.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/using-personas-accessible-design/docview/2533414845/se-2?accountid=10457>
- Wright, D., & Wadhwa, K. (2010). Mainstreaming the e-excluded in Europe: strategies, good practices and some ethical issues. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 12(2), 139–156.
<https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10676-009-9213-y>
- Zhang, J., Brereton, M., Purgathofer, P., Fitzpatrick, G., & Güldenpfennig, F. (2016). Handle the way: Enhancing web accessibility for people with disability. *DIS 2016 Companion - Proceedings of the 2016 ACM Conference on Designing Interactive Systems: Fuse*, 117–120.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/2908805.2909403>